

Project Number:
Project Acronym:

101081883
P2Green
Deliverable 4.3

Horizon Europe Programme
HORIZON-CL6-2022-ZEROPOLLUTION-01

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, under Grant Agreement No°101081883.

Start date of project: 1st December 2022

Duration: 48 months

D 4.3 - Stakeholder engagement strategies

Closing the gap between fork and farm for circular nutrient flows

Deliverable details	
Work Package Title	Building the governance framework
Task Number	T4.2
Deliverable Number	D4.3
Deliverable Title	Stakeholder engagement strategies
Revision Number	
Responsible Organisation	CBS
Author(s)	Anna Schmid, Albina Dioba and Isabel Froes
Due Date	Saturday, November 30, 2024
Delivered Date	Tuesday, November 26, 2024
Reviewed by	ICLEI
Dissemination level	PU
Please cite as	Schmid, A., Dioba, A. & Froes, I., D4.3 Stakeholder engagement strategies, 2024
Contact person EC	Sofia Pachini

Contributing partners	
1.	AGRATHAER GMBH – Germany (Coordinator)
2.	LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FUR GEMUSE- UND ZIERPFLANZENBAU GROSSBEEREN/ERFURT EV – Germany
3.	VILLE DE PARIS – France
4.	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE DUBLIN, NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, DUBLIN – Ireland
5.	SVERIGES LANTBRUKSUNIVERSITET - Sweden
6.	COPENHAGEN BUSINESS SCHOOL - Denmark
7.	LUONNONVARAKESKUS - Finland
8.	NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND MAYNOOTH - Ireland
9.	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS - Greece
10.	BIOAZUL, SL - Spain
11.	CIP CITIZENS IN POWER - Cyprus
12.	KWB Barnim- Germany
13.	GOLDEIMER GEMEINNUTZIGE GMBH - Germany
14.	INSTITUT D'ARQUITECTURA AVANçada DE CATALUNYA - Spain
15.	ICLEI EUROPEAN SECRETARIAT GMBH (ICLEI EUROPASEKRETARIAT GMBH) - Germany
16.	FUNDACION CENTRO ANDALUZ DE INVESTIGACIONES DEL AGUA - Spain

17.	SUN GLOBAL CHEMICALS SERVICES SL - Spain
18.	IRIDRA SRL - Italy
19.	ECOLE NATIONALE DES PONTS ET CHAUSSEES - France
20.	KOZGAZDASAG- ES REGIONALIS TUDOMANYI KUTATOKOZPONT - Hungary
21.	HAFENCITY UNIVERSITAT HAMBURG - Germany
22.	SUSTCHEM TECHNIKI SYMVOULEFTIKI ANONYMI ETAIREIA - Greece
23.	TRANSITION APS - Denmark
24.	TRIODOS BANK NV - Netherlands
25.	MOVERIM CONSULTING SPRL - Belgium
26.	SOCIEDAD AGRARIA DE TRANSFORMACION TROPS N 2803 DE RESPONSABILIDAD LIMITADA - Spain
27.	AGRI SMART DATA SL - Spain
28.	TOUCH DOWN GOTLAND AB - Sweden
29.	SANITATION360 AB - Sweden
30.	GOTLANDS BRYGGERI AB - Sweden
31.	AGUAS Y SANEAMIENTOS DE LA AXARQUIA SA - Spain
32.	VunaNexus - Switzerland

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List of abbreviations:

D	Deliverable
N	Nitrogen
P	Phosphorus
SE	Stakeholder engagement
SoMe	Social Media
T	Task
WS	Workshop

1. Executive Summary

Stakeholder engagement (SE) is an essential yet complex aspect of governance and organizational practice. The methodology for SE was developed through a community-led, co-creation approach, drawing on established literature and practical experience from other EU projects. The primary goal of task 4.2 is to co-create strategies that empower and engage local businesses and stakeholders in the development of regional networks necessary for the operationalization of P2Green's innovative systems.

This task, which spans the entire project timeline (M1 to M48), aims to develop and implement community-led strategies to facilitate stakeholder engagement and carry out a market assessment of the pilot regions.

The first section of the report covers the market assessment, which was conducted in the three pilot regions, examining socio-economic factors, regulatory obstacles, cultural perceptions, and potential growth opportunities for source-separating sanitation systems. The initial search was conducted on Web of Science and Google Scholar, including articles, reports, and legislative text published between 2003 and October 15, 2023 (Moons et al., 2021). Based on predefined inclusion criteria, we developed a string of search terms adopted from related reviews and the Project material (Lam et al., 2015; Corrin & Papadopoulos, 2018; Gwara, 2021). Key identified concerns include low user acceptance of P2Green technologies, as well as regulatory barriers at regional and EU levels, particularly for human excreta-based fertilizers in Sweden and Germany.

The second and following sections of the report cover the SE strategies, which focused on crafting core messages to attract public, private, and business stakeholders while adapting to the local contexts of each pilot region.

The key objectives of the co-creation process include:

- Understanding the specific national and regional contexts of nitrogen and phosphorus (N&P) recovery in pilot regions.
- Mapping, ranking, and analysing relevant stakeholders in these regions.
- Developing actions to engage stakeholders and address their needs and challenges concerning N&P recovery.

In total, seven co-creation workshops were organised across pilot regions, starting with an initial cross-consortium workshop in M1, in January 2023. The workshop helped identify key stakeholders. The stakeholder list was fed into a document to serve as a live database, which has been continuously used by the pilot partners and overall consortium to track and expand their local networks. Additional three online and in-person workshops held in May and June 2023 (M5 & M6) facilitated engagement with local stakeholders in Spain, Sweden, and Germany. These workshops highlighted challenges, needs, and benefits relevant to stakeholders, and helped assess their levels of engagement. For example, a lack of clarity and safety in the envisioned outcomes of the transformation was highlighted by the stakeholders in the German pilot. In the Spanish pilot governance issues and mediating with administrative bodies were highlighted as challenges.

Subsequently, during the M11 in November 2023 Consortium Meeting, three sprints were held to address early-stage stakeholder engagement challenges, focusing on developing strategies and tools to overcome these barriers. These events led to the creation of concrete guidelines for crafting and adapting core messages to maintain and further spark stakeholder interest. Additionally, communication strategies were refined to effectively communicate without overburdening stakeholders.

This report presents the co-created, community-led stakeholder engagement strategies developed for the three P2Green pilot regions, which cover aspects of knowledge and awareness, communication activities, resources, and administration of stakeholder management. These strategies offer practical guidelines for sparking interest among diverse public, private, and business stakeholders, ensuring effective and sustained engagement throughout the project's timeline.

The final section of the report presents the outcome of a feedback survey that was carried out internally within the consortium, to evaluate the stakeholder engagement methodology, offering valuable insights into the effectiveness and areas for improvement within the SE process.

2. Introduction

P2GreeN, a Horizon Europe Innovation Action, aims to transform the linear resource and nutrient flows within the agri-food supply chain into a circular system connecting urban and rural areas. By following the 3R principle - Reduce, Reuse, Recover - P2GreeN focuses on restoring the water-agri-food system and promoting sustainable food practices. The project provides innovative alternatives to reduce dependency on mineral fertilizers, offering green bio-based fertilizers to alleviate pressure on natural resources, particularly water and soil. To achieve these goals, P2GreeN will develop blueprints and circular governance solutions for transitioning from "fork to farm," eliminating nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) by establishing circular nutrient flows between urban and rural infrastructures.

Central to the project are its pilot regions, Gotland in Sweden, the metropolitan area of Hamburg-Hanover in Germany, and the La Axarquía region in Spain. In these regions, P2GreeN is implementing and testing circular value chains that recover N and P from urban human sanitary waste and convert them into safe bio-based fertilizers for agriculture. The insights and experiences gained will be used to replicate and expand these circular solutions in four follower regions - Hungary, Italy, France, and Greece.

Ensuring that diverse perspectives, needs, and expertise of key players across the urban-rural spectrum are integrated into the process of P2GreeN's innovative system solutions is crucial. The implementation in P2GreeN's pilots and follower regions requires active collaboration between policymakers, farmers, urban planners, businesses, and local communities. By involving stakeholders from the beginning, P2GreeN can better address socio-economic and cultural barriers, align solutions with local needs, and foster ownership and commitment to the project's objectives. Furthermore, stakeholder input is vital for creating effective governance frameworks and business models that are feasible and scalable across different regions. Engaging stakeholders also supports the replication of P2GreeN's circular economy models in varied contexts, helping ensure that the project's innovative solutions are adopted and sustained long-term across Europe.

This deliverable provides a comprehensive report on the stakeholder engagement activities carried out in WP4. It outlines the strategies, workshops, and events that were implemented to facilitate early and effective engagement with key stakeholders across the project's pilot and follower regions. The report highlights the steps taken to build regional stakeholder networks, essential for the operationalization of P2GreeN's innovative system solutions, and assesses the impact of these efforts on fostering collaboration and advancing the project's goals.

The report is structured as follows:

- **Market Assessment:** The first section presents the market assessments for each of P2Green's pilot regions (section 3 Market assessment).
- **Stakeholder engagement process:** The second section presents the outcomes of all stakeholder engagement activities carried out during the reporting period (see section 4 Stakeholder engagement process). Three main activities took place:
 - o Workshop 1 (WS1): Initial stakeholder mapping
 - o Workshop 2 (WS2): Stakeholder engagement
 - o Workshop 3 (WS3): Co-developing community-led strategies
- **Stakeholder engagement strategies:** The third section outlines community-led stakeholder engagement strategies, offering guidelines for crafting and adapting the 'core message' to spark interest among diverse public, private, and business stakeholders across the three P2Green pilot regions (see section 5 Stakeholder engagement strategies).
- **Feedback survey:** The final section presents the outcomes of a consortium internal feedback survey on the stakeholder engagement methodology carried out (see section 6. Feedback survey).

3. Market assessment

3.1 Objectives and process

A comprehensive market assessment was conducted to analyse the socio-economic contexts in the P2Green pilot regions, identifying both assets and obstacles that could impact businesses' success. This assessment includes an examination of regulations, cultural and social perceptions, and emerging trends, aiming to understand and identify factors enabling or restricting business growth.

A comprehensive literature review was conducted to examine the recovery and utilization of human excreta, as well as water reclamation in the agricultural sector across Spain, Germany, and Sweden. The initial search was conducted on Web of Science and Google Scholar, including articles, reports, and legislative text published between 2003 and October 15, 2023 (Moons et al., 2021). Based on predefined inclusion criteria, we developed a string of search terms adopted from related reviews and the Project material (Lam et al., 2015; Corrin & Papadopoulos, 2018; Gwara, 2021):

“Nutrient recovery” OR “Re-utilization of nutrients” OR “Circular nutrient flow” OR “Bio-based fertilizer” OR “Nutrient cycle” OR “Urine separation” OR “Nutrient cycle of dry toilets” OR “human waste” OR “fecal sludge” OR “human manure” OR “solid waste” OR “humanure” OR “feces” OR “wastewater use” OR “water reclamation” OR “reclaimed water” AND “agriculture” AND “Sweden” OR “Germany” OR “Spain”.

A total of 41 articles met the full-text inclusion criteria, 10 articles were coded for the Swedish market assessment, 11 for the Spanish, and 20 for the German. Additionally, 17 regulatory and policy documents were included in the analysis, numbered in order of appearance in the text and listed individually at the end of the report. The market assessment specifically focuses on understanding source separation, water reclamation, and human excreta recycling within the complex context of the P2Green pilot regions. The first step of analysis involved categorizing data into themes related to *socio-economic trends*, *cultural and social perceptions*, and *regulatory aspects*, using NVivo 14 software to code the literature. This allowed for a comprehensive evaluation of collected data. Within these themes, paper citations were coded and finally reoccurring themes across the dataset were collected and summarised (Miles et al., 2019). Throughout the coding process, stringent measures were taken to ensure data integrity.

3.2 Spain

The region of La Axarquía, located in Andalusia, southern Spain, is a key producer of sub-tropical crops in Europe, balancing rural agricultural areas with tourist-populated coastal zones. The region, located in Malaga province, faces persistent water scarcity, groundwater overuse, and the risk of desertification, with wastewater contributing to the pollution of the Mediterranean Sea. Due to its Mediterranean climate and high agricultural demands, as well as its limited natural water resources and a growing population driven by tourism, the region faces challenges in meeting its water needs (Rodríguez-Villanueva & Sauri, 2021).

To address this, the local government initiated the conversion of wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) in 2021 to provide reclaimed wastewater for irrigation, aiming to

mitigate farmers' reluctance and control nutrient supply. By treating wastewater to stringent standards, reclaimed water could offer a sustainable alternative to freshwater, particularly in agriculture, which is vital for the region's economy. As one of the main agricultural producers in Europe, Spain is dependent on the export of crops and the high demand of water use to maintain their production volume. Within Spain, around 30% of their irrigated land is located in Andalusia, which is also one of the driest regions of the country. Further, the high production level led to one of the highest greenhouse concentrations worldwide and an overexploitation of groundwater (Gallego-Valero et al., 2019; López-Serrano et al., 2021). For example, avocado and mango crops, which are prevalent in the region of La Axarquía, require constant irrigation throughout the entire growing season, making reclaimed water an invaluable resource to supplement decreasing freshwater sources during dry spells. This approach could not only safeguard the environment but also support economic resilience by ensuring a consistent water supply for agricultural production, even during droughts.

At the P2GreeN test site, technology provider Bioazul is employing a Water Reclamation Plant to produce reclaimed water using treated wastewater, after secondary treatment, from the municipal wastewater treatment plant in Algarrobo. The advanced tertiary treatment ensures removal of pathogens, suspended solids, and other contaminants, transforming the treated wastewater into nutrient rich effluent. This process can produce 3650 m³ of reclaimed water per year. Reclaimed water is then used to fertigate avocado and mango crops and, if needed, it is supplemented by mineral fertilizers or diluted with local water, under the control of an innovative smart fertigation tool (SFT). The SFT provides information on nutrient levels, and elements in the soil affecting the development of crops. The Spanish test site is fostering a sustainable and circular approach to nutrients and water resource utilization in the region. The field trials and governance development with local authorities, aim to counteract drought risks, avoid soil pollution, and raise awareness among farmers and other relevant stakeholders.

Socio-economic trends:

- *Forefront of Europe:* At the European level, around 1,000 Hm³/year of reclaimed water is utilized, making up roughly 2.4% of treated wastewater in the EU. Spain is at the forefront of European reuse, accounting for nearly half of the total volume and ranking fifth globally in installed capacity. Approximately 27% of the 2,000 WWTPs in Spain employ tertiary treatments, including advanced technologies like membranes and advanced oxidation. However, distribution across Spain is uneven, with over 80% of reuse concentrated in water-stressed regions like the Valencian Community, Murcia, Andalusia, Canary Islands, and Balearic Islands. Murcia Region leads with a close to 90% reuse rate, with agricultural irrigation as the main user (IDRA, 2021).
- *Scarcity of conventional water supplies:* The reuse of treated wastewater for agricultural irrigation is likely to intensify due to the scarcity of conventional water supplies, droughts, and the high cost of desalination (Rodríguez-Villanueva, & Sauri, 2021). Besides the agricultural context, scholars also mention the high-water demand of green areas and recreational areas such as golf courses in the region. For example, Spain irrigates around 300 golf courses with a total water demand of 80 hm³/year (Jodar-Abellan, López-Ortiz &

Melgarejo-Moreno, 2019). Reclaimed water holds promise as a valuable contributor to urban water supplies through direct use or indirect support of the conventional wastewater systems. However, the increasing presence of new pollutants and the flows of increased stormwaters, due to climate changes, are present challenges that wastewater treatment plants need to address (Rodríguez-Villanueva & Sauri, 2021). The scholars highlight a test site in the metropolitan area of Barcelona, arguing that wastewater treatment plants could be transformed into bio factories, replacing energy consumption and waste generation with energy generation and resource retrieval, to face upcoming challenges. However, treated wastewater itself may become scarce, leading to potential conflicts among local farmers, businesses, and policy makers (Rodríguez-Villanueva & Sauri, 2021).

- *Sustainable agriculture movements*: The growing movement towards sustainable and regenerative agriculture can create opportunities for the use of reclaimed wastewater as a more sustainable resource compared to freshwater. Already, reclaimed water is primarily used in the agricultural sector for the irrigation of various crops, accounting for more than 40% of the total reused wastewaters in Spain. In comparison, industrial use of reclaimed water only accounts to 10% of the total reused wastewaters in Spain (Jodar-Abellan, López-Ortiz & Melgarejo-Moreno, 2019). The Royal Decree 1620/2007 [2], which established the legal regime of water reuse in Spain, was a significant step in regulating wastewater reuse by clarifying responsibilities and defining quality standards for each possible use of reclaimed water. However, scholars argue for the need for a mechanism to enhance reuse and align existing installations with the highest quality requirements. This could encourage sustainable and regenerative agriculture (Jodar-Abellan, López-Ortiz & Melgarejo-Moreno, 2019).
- *Technology advancements*: Advances in wastewater treatment technologies can reduce costs and enhance the efficiency of making reclaimed water available for irrigation. López-Serrano et al. (2021) argue that the use of reclaimed water can increase economic profit of farmers through reduced fertilization, which can be reduced by up to 66%, also supporting soil fertility and fruit quality. However, the high cost of reclaimed water compared to natural water resources often makes water reuse less attractive to farmers in Spain. Technical challenges in implementing water reuse infrastructure, including treatment technologies and distribution systems, also hinder the adoption of reclaimed water use (Ballesteros-Olza et al., 2022). However, López-Serrano et al. (2021) stress the importance of developing infrastructures to potentiate the implementation of reclaimed water, describing it as a resource proven to be sustainable and cost-effective.

These trends highlight the complex interplay of institutional, economic, and social elements that influence the use of reclaimed water for agricultural irrigation in La Axarquía region. Especially, water scarcity and climate change are pressing factors in the shift towards water reclamation. On one hand, the lack of infrastructure to transport that water from the WWT plants to the end user. On the other hand, concerns about the quality/safety of that water. Technical difficulties to the implementation of a re-use infrastructure are hindering the uptake of water reclamation. Furthermore, the elevated expense of reclaimed water in comparison to natural sources of water makes water

reuse economically less appealing to farmers. Sustainable movements and test sites can support the development of new installations and function as a best-practice example to other regions.

Cultural and social perceptions:

- **Acceptance of reclaimed water:** One of the main challenges connected to water reclamation. Especially, the public concern over pathogens is highlighted. Concerns about reclaimed water can be divided into:
 - Consumer-level concerns about the sanitary safety of the water and whether it is safe to consume food irrigated with reclaimed water. The acceptance of reclaimed water usage for irrigation is connected to cultural norms. Especially, concerns about sanitary risks enforce the stigma associated with using treated wastewater for agriculture. Additionally, Ballesteros-Olza et al. (2022) describe a 'yuck factor' they recognized at a test site in the greater Madrid area. They observed disgusted reactions of stakeholders at the idea of using reclaimed water on fruit crops. Additionally, the perception of sanitary risks by consumers is described as a critical factor in advancing the use of reclaimed water for irrigation.
 - Farmer-level concerns about the water quality (salt content, electrical conductivity) and the potential negative impact on crops. However, farmers seem to be aware of the ability of reclaimed water to secure water supply and to fertilize and provide nutrients, as well as being a cost-saving alternative to fresh water (Ballesteros-Olza et al., 2022). Mesa-Pérez and Berbel (2020) highlight that the perception of key stakeholders differs depending on the level of water scarcity and the significance of irrigated agriculture in their immediate context.

Further, lack of effective institutional structures, inadequate leadership, and insufficient socio-political initiatives may undermine the execution and expansion of water reuse programs (Ballesteros-Olza et al., 2022). There are several physicochemical parameters not regulated by the royal decree, which can still render water that meets legal standards unsuitable for irrigating certain crops.

- **Public awareness and education:** Given the seriousness of water scarcity and high agricultural activities, Spain focuses on social, governance, and market-related strengths concerning reclaimed water to increase societal awareness. Increasing societal and consumers acceptance are major aspects to present reclaimed water as a solid alternative to freshwater use (Mesa-Pérez & Berbel, 2020). Profound and long-term information dissemination is crucial to address public perceptions and ensure good communication. The keystone in the implementation and societal dissemination of reclaimed water for irrigation is the development of the Regulation EU-2020/741 Minimum Requirements for Water Reuse [3]. The existence of reclamation standards, and good communication with users are considered as strengths in promoting the use of reclaimed water on local, regional as well as national level (Mesa-Pérez & Berbel, 2020). Despite many positive aspects derived from the use of treated wastewater to irrigate crops, its low implementation rate seems to be connected to farmers' perceptions due to the persistent inability to receive the economic,

social, and environmental benefits derived from its use. Literature highlights the need to illustrate the economic benefits to farmers to enhance the sustainability of their agriculture exploitations in the long run (López-Serrano, et al., 2021). Examples from regions like Murcia (IDRA, 2021), with a high percentage of wastewater reuse could support social acceptance and function as upscaling case scenario.

Increasing the awareness and acceptance of reclaimed water should be the keystone for local, national, and European strategies to foster its usage in agriculture. The focus can be put on transparency and social trust to counteract fears or consumer resistance. Further, well-established risk assurance systems can increase social acceptance and the implementation of wastewater reclamation technologies (Mesa-Pérez & Berbel, 2020).

Regulations:

- *EU directives and regulations:* EU directives and regulations, including Directive 91/271/EEC [4] and the Water Framework Directive (WFD) [5], advocate for the cost-recovery principle in water-related services. In 2018, the EU proposed regulations to encourage water reuse for agricultural irrigation and environmental purposes and this legislation enabled wastewater reclamation and reuse in Spain. Consequently, taxes in Spain have been adjusted to fund wastewater treatment services and improve water quality (Mesa-Pérez & Berbel, 2020). Especially, agricultural water abstraction mechanisms were implemented. These systems aim to recuperate the expenses associated with regulation, storage, and management of basin-level water services. They align with the requirements outlined in the WFD, with different levels of cost recovery being observed (Berbel et al., 2019). Since 2020, reclaimed water is also part of the EU's circular economy, with regulation 2020/741 [3] aiming to standardize reclaimed water quality and risk management systems across member states. This, along with global initiatives like the UN 2030 Agenda, the Sustainable Development Goals, and the EU Circular Economy Action Plan, promotes wider adoption of reclaimed water reuse for irrigation, offering a promising solution amid water resource pressures (Ballesteros-Olza et al., 2022; Mesa-Pérez & Berbel, 2020).
- *Safety standards on national level:* The EU Water Reuse Regulation [6] is anticipated to promote reclaimed water use in agriculture. This regulation is expected to address trade barriers for agricultural products, establish standardized water quality requirements, and enhance social acceptance through improved risk management processes (Ballesteros-Olza et al., 2022). Agricultural extensification and public awareness campaigns both led to positive outcomes as stressed by Ballesteros-Olza et al. (2022). However, only public awareness initiatives increased water reuse, while agricultural extensification primarily reduced water abstractions and pollution. In Spain, wastewater treatment and reuse are regulated by the EU Directive of 1991 on Urban Wastewater Treatment, which aims to protect the environment from the adverse effects of urban wastewater discharges. The directive is incorporated into Spanish law 11/95 and by the Spanish Royal Decree 1620/2007 on reuse of treated wastewater [2]. Besides the fact that Spain was fined for not complying with EU standards, the country holds a leading position in Europe

regarding water reuse, primarily for agricultural irrigation (Rodríguez-Villanueva & Sauri, 2021).

- *Lack of institutional coordination on a local level:* The use of reclaimed water for irrigation is hampered by institutional aspects, public resistance, and high costs (Ballesteros-Olza et al., 2022). Lack of institutional coordination, complex regulations, and delays imposed by administrative procedures are identified as barriers. Supportive frameworks and clear institutional arrangements are needed to facilitate reclaimed water reuse projects. Political support could facilitate the bureaucratic process and foster reclaimed water use (Ballesteros-Olza et al., 2022).

These regulations and policies aim to empower businesses, particularly in the agricultural sector, by providing a more sustainable and reliable water source through reclaimed water, thus potentially enabling growth opportunities in regions like La Axarquía. However, reclaimed water usage for irrigation faces social, cultural, and economic barriers, including high costs for farmers and public apprehension on water quality. Despite being recognized for its benefits in securing water supply and providing nutrients, concerns regarding sanitary risks hinder its acceptance. Addressing these challenges through social awareness campaigns and compliance with new regulations could unlock growth opportunities in the region, emphasizing the need to address social, cultural, economic, and institutional challenges to promoting reclaimed water use in agriculture.

3.3 Germany

Germany faces significant challenges regarding water and soil pollution, intensified by climate change, wastewater management and intensive farming practices. As one of Europe's largest economies, Germany's industrial and agricultural activities contribute to various pollutants entering water bodies, including rivers, lakes, and groundwater. Climate change intensifies these issues, leading to more frequent and intense rainfall events, which can overwhelm sewage systems and agricultural runoff, carrying pollutants into waterways. Major pressures on rivers and groundwater resources in Germany are diffuse agriculture pollution, with 65% of rivers being affected and 41% of groundwater reservoirs (Gruère, Shigemitsu & Crawford, 2020). Especially, high levels of nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) pollution in water bodies stem from intense farming in rural zones and wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) discharges in urban regions. The dominant wastewater system in Germany consists of sewers draining to WWTP, with a majority of 96% of German households linked to the in most cases public system, connecting nearly 10,000 treatment facilities with tertiary treatment. Most wastewater passes through a process that eliminates targeted nutrients. The well-established sewage system, and mandatory connection of each German household to it, is argued to be a hindering factor in the shift towards more innovative sanitation and recovery systems (DWA, 2010). Alternatives to the established sewage system are dry source-separating toilets facilitating targeted nutrient recovery and contaminant removal from human waste. These toilets operate without the need for water to flush waste, instead utilizing standardized waste containers to transport and manage human waste. By avoiding the use of water for flushing, dry toilets offer significant water savings, making them particularly appealing in regions where water scarcity is a concern. Additionally, they contribute to environmental conservation by

reducing water pollution and sewage treatment costs (DIN, 2020). While still relatively uncommon compared to traditional toilets, the adoption of dry and source separation toilets in Germany is gradually increasing, driven by growing environmental awareness and the desire for more sustainable sanitation solutions.

In the German pilot, Kreiswerke Barnim (KWB) has installed a container based liquid human waste VunaNexus (VN) system treatment facility with a treatment capacity for approximately 100 m³/yr urine. To produce certified Aurin® a third process step will be implemented in cooperation with VN, the distiller. VN will install the distiller and will also take care of necessary adjustments, operation and maintenance of the system to reach the required quality level for Aurin production. The Aurin® fertiliser will be marketed by VN. KWB will be responsible for collection and all logistics related to the human liquid waste collection and handling. Goldeimer (GE) will collect mainly dry toilet contents from festivals, allotment gardens and off-grid nature tourism destinations. A thermophilic container-based composting plant for faeces will be set up, further automating the technology developed by GE's network partner Finizio, and operated by GE on the Vagtshoff farm in lower saxony near Hamburg. The Vagtshoff farmers provide industrial waste heat and biochar for the composting facility, as well as the agricultural area (10 ha) for fertiliser application. Both faecal compost (~40 t[dm]/yr) and Aurin® fertilisers will be used to grow agricultural crops. During the project period, changes regarding pilot partners in the German pilot took place (2nd Amendment). These changes were communicated continuously and were considered in this market assessment. The market assessment focuses on a national level, through which the changes in the pilot configuration did not affect the quality of the workflow.

Socio-economic trends:

- *Need for close cycle management:* Negative impacts of climate change will continuously challenge the German infrastructure. Droughts, lack of fresh water or storms make it urgent to promote policy changes and actions for mobilizing the existing and national resources to accelerate the sustainable transition (Keuter, et. al., 2021; Nelles, Grünes & Morscheck, 2016). The authors also argue for circular production and resource recovery highlighting City Regional food systems (CRFS) interlinking different sectoral systems. The transition of sanitation and nutrient recovery enables the efficient circulation of local nutrients between urban areas and agriculture (Keuter, et al., 2021). In Germany, waste management has been under transition over the last decades moving towards a more sustainable and circular approach, making circular solutions like sanitary waste recovery increasingly realistic. By 2016, closed cycle management already contributed 20% in achieving the German Kyoto targets on reducing climate-relevant emissions (Nelles, Grünes & Morscheck, 2016).

The German Association of water management (DWA) describes novel sanitary systems (NASS) as an alternative, promising higher flexibility in adapting to changing environmental conditions. Neligan (2018) further highlights the need to increase the digitalisation of such processes, to ensure an efficient resource recovery from human excreta. Back in 2010, DWA already claimed that the existing sewer system was reaching its limits while nutrients in significant quantities (e.g. nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium) were available in the sewage. These nutrients are largely neglected as a resource in Germany.

Häfner et al. (2023) describe human urine and feces as major contributors to the nutrient load in sewage, for example, 80% of Nitrogen and up to 60% of Phosphorus. In comparison to the current sewage treatment, a resource-centred system would save fresh water, reduce chemical pollutants, increase recycling, and fosters resource efficiency (ZirkulierBAR, 2023). In Switzerland and Austria fertilizers based on P and N recovered from human urine are already on the market demonstrating their demand and feasibility (ZirkulierBAR, 2023). However, they are not widely spread and are not licensed for the German market (DIN, 2020).

- *Increase in market value and demand:* A shortage in P and N as well as a lack of natural freshwater reservoirs contribute to the increasing market value of nutrient recovery solutions. Keuter et al. (2021) argue that the pressing question for the future of agriculture is how to achieve higher yields despite the substantial energy demands of fertilizer production and the ongoing contamination of water and soil with phosphorus and reactive nitrogen. City Regional Food Systems (CRFS) could be a solution to these problems. However, to ensure sustainable CRFSs, innovative technologies and methods need to be further developed and evaluated for the German market (Keuter et al., 2021).

Some technologies and methods are already experiencing higher demand. For example, the market for mobile dry toilets has been expanding over the last few years (DIN, 2020). For separately collected solid waste, this involves sanitizing and stabilizing composting. In this process, a particularly high-temperature aerobic treatment method eliminates pathogenic germs from the dry toilet residue. The result is high-quality compost that can be reintroduced into agriculture as a recycling fertilizer. But also separately collected liquid toilet contents can be processed into marketable liquid recycling fertilizers through nitrification and activated carbon adsorption. Nearly all trace substances, such as pharmaceuticals, drugs, and hormones, are removed through activated carbon filtration (Köpping et al., 2020). Another advantage is that by separately collecting and treating the nutrient-rich urine, sewage treatment plants can experience significant relief for energy-intensive nitrogen removal (ZirkulierBAR, 2023). Additionally, the demand for alternative fertilizers is on the rise as a substitute for chemical fertilizers (Dadrasina et al., 2021). Neligan (2018) highlights that the private sector plays a key role in shifting towards a more circular approach and resource recovery. The scholar argues that resource scarcity is pressuring the German economy towards resource efficiency, fostering both economic and environmental self-interest in the efficient use of materials. Horbach and Rammer (2020) argue that, despite initial implementation costs, circular innovations in waste recycling eventually led to cost efficiency.

- *Success stories:* Uncertainties surrounding innovative infrastructure, such as N&P recovery and urban sanitation waste recovery, can hinder the growth of such implementations. However, success stories from existing test regions and implementations can overcome uncertainties. Skambraks et al. (2016) describe a pilot region in Hamburg that was supported by the authorities to create a successful example of resource recovery implementation. This initiative also served as an advocate at both the regional and national levels. Also, the sanitary recycling Eschborn (SANIRESCH) project, highlights in their

experiments, that yields with urine-based fertilizer were higher in comparison to samples without fertilizer. Successful use cases are argued to increase social acceptance and upscaling (Arnold & Schmidt, 2012). Committed stakeholders as well as strong sustainable project drivers are also defined as enablers of a successful implementation. Furthermore, a long-term engagement strategy aiming for broad acceptance is argued to be important for successful implementation and usage. Skambraks et al. (2016) argue that early-stage pilot sites are driven by university and academic collaborations, while test sites in later stages are supported by governmental collaborations and initiatives. Successful projects and pilot test sites are defined as essential prerequisites for long-term implementation and upscaling (Skambraks et al., 2016). Pilot projects can also increase acceptance among decision-makers and the public. In addition, a technical set of rules and binding legal specifications can be developed based on such pioneering projects (DWA, 2008). However, due to the well-established wastewater disposal systems and legal barriers in Germany, innovative sanitation systems have received limited attention beyond test sites. Therefore, every new project is crucial for accumulating experience in the planning, construction, and operation phases (Skambraks et al., 2016; Arnold & Schmidt, 2012).

- *Environmental goals:* Local and national sustainability standards and regional strategies can encourage projects and increase their success (Skambraks et al., 2016). The authors highlight the case of Hamburg, where local environmental objectives for the Jenfelder Au, a newly designed green area, target a climate-neutral community. This involves the utilization of renewable energy sources for heating and electricity, alongside a conscientious approach to resource usage, particularly water preservation and source separation sewage systems. The scholars argue that local implementation and realization of environmental goals through such test sites has a direct impact on the region. The scholars further highlight the effectiveness of local projects compared to national or top-down goals. Skambraks et al. (2016) define concrete regional or local environmental and governmental goals as drivers for innovation in the field of N&P recovery.
- *Administrative and governance issues:* In recent years, countries like Germany, Austria, and Switzerland have seen the rise of a new market involving mobile dry toilets for events and permanent installations in settings such as allotment gardens or mobile homes. Especially, start-ups and small to medium-sized companies picked-up business models based on ecologically (chemical-free) operated and well-serviced toilets in public spaces. However, the growth of this emerging industry faces obstacles stemming from administrative, legal, and economic uncertainties. The uncertainties primarily revolve around soil treatment strategies, as well as the sales and utilization prospects for fertilizers derived from dry toilet content. This highlights the high complexity of establishing human-based fertilizers in the market (Krause et al., 2021). Skambraks et al. (2016) underscore the challenges associated with implementing new and innovative infrastructure systems. For instance, uncertainties in assigning stakeholder responsibilities, rigid organizational structures, financial concerns, and unclear legal regulations can impede growth for companies in the sector.

The socio-economic trends identified for the German pilot region, show the interplay between pressing environmental issues such as water scarcity and water pollution, making resource recovery a potential alternative to existing principles. Concrete environmental goals addressing local context as well as successful pilot sites can foster the development of a source separation system. However, hindering administrative and lacking governance aspects slow down the innovation process.

Cultural and Social perceptions:

- *Knowledge acquisition:* When implementing source separation technologies, it is considered essential to gather information on user acceptance, regulatory requirements, cross-sectorial stakeholder networks. For this, designated pilot areas can serve as a means to gain insights into the overall environmental impacts and societal performance during their operational phases (Skambraks, 2016). Further, Keuter et al. (2021) argue that innovative processes such as bio-based fertilizer production need to be integrated into long-term social transformation processes to enhance the acceptance of food derived from recycled materials. Moreover, there is a desire for cross-sector collaboration among stakeholders and experts. A notable internal motivation, as highlighted by leaders involved in current and forthcoming pilot projects, is the pursuit of knowledge to effectively tackle potential future challenges in wastewater treatment (Skambraks, 2016).
- *Education and social acceptance:* Krause et al. (2021) highlight the importance of educating stakeholders and the general public on the correct usage of new innovations. Further, easily accessible information and clear guidelines can support social acceptance. Additionally, conducting tests for harmful substances in accordance with local laws and regulations and guaranteeing the production of safe and high-quality fertilizers, can increase social acceptance. The education process also needs to be implemented in the overall process to improve the reception of food made from bio-based fertilizer (Keuter et al., 2021).

Regulations:

The German market, is influenced by European policies such as the Green Deal implemented in 2019, followed by the Circular Economy Action Plan in 2020 and other European initiatives. Both plans outline the EU's objectives and efforts to pave the way for a circular, climate-neutral, and competitive economy by 2050. Further, the EU waste framework directive set five steps for dealing with waste prioritizing re-use, recycling, and recovery (Nelles et al., 2016). On national and federal levels, regulations and acts influence the market for waste handling, water reclamation, and nutrient recovery in Germany.

- The German Circular Economy Act (Kreislaufwirtschaftsgesetz KrWG) [7]: Formulation of a waste prevention program (first introduced in 2012) to promote circular economy and conserve natural resources and ensure the protection of people and the environment in the production and management of waste. To improve the recycling of waste, the obligation to collect waste separately should be strengthened.

- Resource Efficiency Program III (2020-2023) [8]: developing and implementing concepts and procedures to recover phosphorus and other valuable materials from municipal wastewater. The goal is to further develop wastewater and waste treatment from a previously hygiene-focused system to a resource-oriented one.
- DIN-SPEC-91421 is a quality standardization approach of bio-fertilizers derived from human waste: The product specifications (DIN, 2020) aim to enhance the marketability of recycling products in both the German and European markets, thereby facilitating industry development. This effort also seeks to make a sustainability contribution by promoting the establishment of integrated circular economies, achieved through nutrient recycling, and connecting sanitation and food production. This initiative encourages the practical use of recycled fertilizers in horticulture.
- German bio-waste regulation (BioAbfV) [10]: The amendment includes the list of the types of bio-waste suitable for utilisation on land and of other suitable materials. Human excreta or sewage sludge are not defined as waste and therefore not approved for re-use.
- German wastewater ordinance (AbfKlärV) [11]: The regulation defines conditions under which soil-related utilisation of sewage sludge (for fertilisation purposes or for agricultural backfilling) is permissible. It stipulates that all treatment plants must determine the phosphorus content of their sewage sludge and outline how phosphorus recovery is to be implemented by 2032. Due to high contamination of sewage sludge, recycling to soils has been halted. Regulations such as the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD) further reduce the effluent concentration of phosphorous in Germany.
- Fertilizer ordinance (Düngemittelverordnung DüMV) [9]: The DüMV defines that only raw materials listed as permissible in Annex 2 Table 7 of this ordinance may be used for fertilizer production. There is a prohibition on the use of unlisted substances. This includes human feces and urine as raw materials, and consequently, the resulting recycled fertilizer (see § 3(1) of the Fertilizer ordinance) (ZirkulierBAR, 2023). In particular, the inapplicability of the BioAbfV (Biowaste Ordinance) [10] and the DüMV (Fertilizer Ordinance) [9] prevents the production and promotion of recycling fertilizers. This constitutes a significant obstacle to the advancement of recycling fertilizers in Germany. Under the classification of human waste as wastewater, there is a very limited utilization pathway through the AbfKlärV (Wastewater Treatment Ordinance) [11]. However, this limitation includes the subsequent use of the fertilizer, thereby excluding economic market opportunities. Additionally, the use of dry toilets is locally restricted by obligations.

A significant future challenge for humans and farming lies in eliminating unaccounted pollutants in wastewater, such as pharmaceutical residues, hormone-like chemicals, microplastics and per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). German regulations assume that the current wastewater treatment methods cannot address these trace substances. Emerging technologies like special membranes for nutrient recovery seem promising for circular nutrient recovery from human waste. However, there are no established legal standards to guide sewage plant operators in their transition to more resource-oriented sewage methods. Additionally, the fertilisation with human feces derived fertilizers is currently forbidden in the German market. The ministry of

environment is currently developing a "trace substance strategy" [12] that could pave the path for water reuse.

3.4 Sweden

Gotland, Sweden, an island located in the "Baltic Sea dead zone" is affected by excessive eutrophication and hypoxia (Kersch, 2023, p. 9). Around 90% of the Swedish population is connected to traditional wastewater treatment plants, many featuring tertiary denitrification processes that release the inert nitrogen gas into the atmosphere and accumulate the phosphorus in sludge. Yet going to the bathroom in Sweden accounts for 38% of the nitrogen and 29% of the phosphorus released into surface waters from anthropogenic activities. Approximately 25% of the sludge is applied to agricultural fields, enabling some phosphorus reuse but limited nitrogen reuse. Efforts to enhance the recycling rate face challenges due to concerns about unwanted elements, i.e. heavy metals, organic micro pollutants and pathogens contaminating the sludge. A major limitation is the current infrastructural lock-in that de-incentivises the implementation of source separation technologies at a larger scale (McConville et al., 2017a).

In Sweden, source separation efforts started in the early 1990s, by grassroots organisations originating in eco villages, making Sweden a pioneer in the field. By the late 1990s, source separation was picked up by politics and the construction industry. In 1997 the parliament at the time introduced the concept of "The Free People's Home" fostering investment in green development programs and technology. Research further picked up the topic of source separation and several test and pilot projects on urine diversion systems and nutrient recovery were carried out. However, due to lack of emphasis on technological development and functionality of implemented systems, source separation experienced a backlash in the early 2000s. Systems which failed to reuse the collected urine or struggled with effective waste management further down the chain or reuse, were retransformed to standard systems (McConville et al., 2017a). One of the main challenges in Sweden and elsewhere, was the handover of the responsibility to the individual homeowner to manage their source separated fractions while the municipality managed the mixed flow only. In the last decades, due to changes in national and European guidelines such as the Horizon 2020 or the European Green Deal, source separation has regained public interest. Several Swedish municipalities have been testing source separation treatments and implementation it in existing municipal infrastructure. However, scholars highlight the importance for a holistic understanding of nutrient cycles and the implementation to existing infrastructures and estimate the number of urine-diversion toilets in Sweden to 135,000, mostly installed at summer houses or allotment gardens (McConville et al., 2017 b).

Within P2GeeN, the Swedish pilot site aims to transform human urine into dry fertilizer for barley cultivation. The Swedish University of Agricultural Science (SLU) and Sanitation360, demonstrate nutrient recycling from human urine. In the urban area of Visby, processes for urine collection, stabilisation for nutrient retention and solid fertilizer production will be expanded. The resulting fertilizer will be utilized in agriculture for barley cultivation, ultimately contributing to local beer production at Gotland's Bryggeri. This initiative creates a new value chain, reducing nutrient loading in wastewater, enhancing local agriculture and food production. The reclamation

potential of this process for collection at public toilets and urinals is estimated at 900 kg of nitrogen and 90 kg of phosphorous per year. Furthermore, the pilot aims to obtain 150 m³ of urine by the end of 2026 (P2GeeN, 2024). The test site especially aims to demonstrate a full-service chain of nutrient recovery focusing on awareness raising, and capacity building with municipalities, farmers, and other relevant stakeholders in Sweden.

Socio-economic trends:

- *Phosphorus supply and resource limitations:* Previously, there was the belief that rock phosphate was scarce. This suggests that immediate concerns about phosphorus supply may not be warranted. Nonetheless, resources like rock phosphate, potash ores, hydrogen, and energy for ammonia synthesis are finite (Heshmati & Rashidghalam, 2021). If phosphorus is not recycled, its scarcity could lead to a “phosphogeddon”, impacting not only climate change but also food production and quality (Kalaitzidou et al., 2024; Shirai, Leisz & Kyuma, 2023). Highlighting the limited availability of resources can encourage the exploration of alternative fertilizers, such as those derived from human sanitary waste. The discussions in Sweden have moved over from only focusing on the re-circulation of P into also including the recycling of N. The growing interest in urine source separation, particularly in Europe, is environmentally advantageous and relies on the ability to replace synthetic fertilizers with a product that has low nitrogen emissions (Shirai, Leisz & Kyuma, 2023).
- *Climate change and environmental degradation:* The rapid degradation of the environment has led to the development of sustainable strategies. Countries and organizations are increasingly adopting diverse environmental strategies and policies moving away from linear resource usage towards more circular approaches. There is a shift towards recognizing urine as a valuable resource, rich in nutrients, which can be used for fertilizing crops or integrated into industrial processes (Heshmati & Rashidghalam, 2021). Scholars argue that about 5% of P and 30% N are emitted with the outgoing wastewater from treatment plants when they reach their treatment requirements. The trend towards sustainable resource usage can empower businesses that offer eco-friendly solutions, such as converting human waste to fertilizers (Heshmati, & Rashidghalam, 2021).
- *Water scarcity and increasing pollution:* Water scarcity is becoming a pressing issue, impacting human health, economic development, and ecological systems worldwide. Factors like population growth, urbanization, industrial development, and climate change are expected to push up to 50% of the world’s population into water insecurity by 2050. This trend is restricting Swedish businesses that rely heavily on water resources but can also enable businesses that offer solutions to mitigate water scarcity (Lindqvist et al., 2021).
- *Infrastructure lock-in and resource recovery:* Promoting the reuse of human waste within conventional waste and wastewater systems in Sweden faces significant limitations. Challenges arise from the existing infrastructure and the difficulty of optimizing recovery within systems originally designed for different purposes. This can hinder businesses, especially since systems intended for resource recovery in Sweden are frequently overlooked in urban planning processes. This trend highlights the challenges faced by businesses trying to

introduce innovative waste-to-fertilizer solutions in regions with established infrastructure (McConville, et al., 2017a).

- *Emerging test sites*: The P2Green test site in Gotland is part of a global trend wherein efforts are made to separate urine from sewage and recycle it into products such as fertilizer (McConville et al., 2017a). This approach, known as urine diversion, is not only being explored in Gotland but also countries such as the United States, Australia, Switzerland, Ethiopia, and South Africa.

In conclusion, while there are trends that can empower businesses in converting urban sanitary waste to safe bio-based fertilizers in Gotland, there are also significant challenges and restrictions. Environmental pressure and declining resources support the development and implementation of innovative source separation. However, the well-established infrastructure in Sweden can cause a lock-in and hinder new implementation. Understanding these trends and adapting to them can be crucial for businesses aiming to succeed in this domain.

Cultural and social perceptions:

- *Cultural taboos*: There are broader questions of social change and acceptance related to varying levels of cultural taboos around human waste and deeply entrenched conventions about industrial sewage and food systems. This suggests that cultural norms and societal conventions can act as barriers to the acceptance of using human waste as fertilizer (Wald, 2022). In line with this argument, McConville et al. (2017a) highlight the importance of social acceptance as a prerequisite for a long-term implementation of source separation and nutrient recycling technologies.
- *Farmer preferences*: Parfitt (2023) indicates that the physical form and usability of bio-fertilizers can influence its acceptance and usage degree. For example, most farmers in Gotland viewed Sanitation360's dry and pelletized fertilizer favourably. With their experience in spreading this type of fertilizer, farmers can also utilize existing machinery and spreading methods that are compatible with it (Parfitt, 2023).
- *Conflict of values*: In Sweden, there are strong values regarding the public and economic good, which can conflict with environmental priorities and hinder sustainable developments. Conflicting values are also observed in the expansion of the predominant centralized wastewater system or in supporting the establishment of a decentralized approach. Further, values which may drive transition towards nutrient recycling are economic efficiency, risk reduction and the maintenance of existing sewage and wastewater treatment systems (McConville et al., 2017a).
- *Knowledge and awareness*: Many farmers have not been informed about the regulations and possibilities surrounding the use of human urine in agriculture due to such information being presented in jargon-filled legal documents and/or publications. This lack of awareness can act as a barrier to adopting new farming techniques or adjusting existing technologies and infrastructure (Parfitt, 2023).
- *Consumer Acceptance*: There is a divide among experts about consumer acceptance of food fertilized with human urine derived fertilizer. While some believe consumers do not consider the type of fertilizer used, others think consumers might find it repellent or unsafe. This indicates that consumer

perception can be a significant factor in the adoption of such fertilizers, additionally source separated urine often falls under same rules as sewage sludge and is looked upon as sludge, leading to a challenging situation to reuse it as a clean fertiliser. One further challenge is the food industry not wanting to risk anything, thereby not accepting circular fertilisers with the motive that the consumers may not accept it. Additionally, prejudices about the safety of human derived fertilizer need to be overcome across Sweden. The current sanitation system and decades long negative media coverage of the use of sewage sludge in agriculture in Sweden, has likely sensitized the public's view towards the potential use of urine in agriculture as well (Parfitt, 2023).

While there are opportunities and advantages in converting human sanitary waste to safe bio-based fertilizers in Gotland, there are also significant cultural, social, and knowledge-based barriers that need to be addressed. For urine source separation to be successful, farmers and consumers must accept new types of fertilizers as a safe improvement to the current standards. Farmers are already positive towards urine but need to be guaranteed that consumers will be as likely to buy the final food product and that it will not cost them more to choose separated source fertilizers. This indicates that cultural and social perceptions play a significant role in the adoption of such technologies. Engaging with farmers, consumers, and the broader public, and educating stakeholders about the benefits and safety of new practices, is crucial in overcoming the existing social scepticism.

Regulations:

- *National Strategy for Sustainable Development:* In December 2020, the Swedish parliament approved a government bill with an overarching objective for the implementation of the 2030 Agenda. Sweden will implement the 2030 Agenda to achieve economically, socially, and environmentally sustainable development through a coherent policy nationally and internationally. Implementation will be guided by the agenda's 'leave no one behind' principle. This strategy can act as a guiding framework for businesses aiming to adopt sustainable practices, including human waste-to-fertilizer conversion (Heshmati & Rashidghalam, 2021).
- *Circular Economy Delegation:* In 2016, the Swedish government appointed a special investigator for the Circular Economy (CE) who analysed instruments for promoting product utilization and reducing waste generation. This led to the establishment of a Circular Economy Delegation in 2018, aiming to facilitate a transition to a circular, resource-efficient, and bio-based economy at national and regional levels. Such initiatives can empower businesses in the waste-to-fertilizer domain (Heshmati & Rashidghalam, 2021).
- *Swedish Environmental Code:* Since 2006, the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency's Environmental Code for on-site sanitation has shifted from prescribing specific technologies to setting functional requirements. However, these functional requirements do not apply to actions on a household level. This regulatory shift can both enable and restrict businesses depending on their technological solutions (McConville et al., 2017a).
- *Challenges with source separation on a local level:* While municipalities like Helsingborg are exploring source separation within existing wastewater jurisdictions, the practice is still in its development stages. The expansion of

wastewater jurisdictions using decentralized technologies and source separation is being explored in other municipalities such as Malmö and Gothenburg. This indicates a trend towards source separation, which can empower businesses in this domain (McConville et al., 2017a).

- *Classification of Waste Fractions*: In Sweden, source-separated toilet waste fractions are classified as household waste, making them the responsibility of the municipality and its solid waste service provider. However, the application of the Environmental Code on these fractions is relatively untested, indicating potential regulatory challenges for businesses (McConville et al., 2017a).
- Certification of source-separated wastewater fractions (SPCR 178) [15]: Quality assurance for source-separated wastewater fractions under SPCR 178 is a commitment to ensure structured operations and traceability of source-separated wastewater fractions (urine, feces, blackwater, and brown water). The requirements set by the certification system are controlled by RISE, an independent organisation, which contributes to increasing end users' confidence in the product. Within P2Green the pilot aims to meet the certification standards to improve acceptance of their fertilizer.
- SNFS 1994:2 [16]: is a Swedish regulation that defines the management and treatment of wastewater. It outlines guidelines and standards for the design, construction, and operation of small-scale wastewater treatment plants and the usage of sewage sludge in agriculture. These regulations aim to ensure that such facilities meet certain quality and environmental standards to protect public health and the environment.
- SJVFS 2004:62 [17]: is a law on environmental considerations in agriculture about the application of organic fertilizers. To be classified as bio-fertilizer, human urine-derived fertilizer needs to meet the standards defined by the law.
- *Lack of Streamlined Norms*: A significant bottleneck for future diffusion is the absence of streamlined norms and standards for urine source-separating technologies. The lack of norms for source-separating toilets can restrict businesses from investing in novel toilet designs (Larsen et al., 2021).

In conclusion, while there are regulations in place that empower businesses in converting human sanitary waste to safe bio-based fertilizers in Sweden, there are also significant regulatory challenges related to the lack of norms for source-separating toilets that need to be addressed. Introducing urine source separation requires a new type of toilet, separate piping and storage for urine, and a new type of treatment technology. These requirements can pose challenges for businesses in terms of infrastructure and investment. Developing environmental regulations to set precedents could be the initial step for upscaling. Further, decentralization and alternative organizational structures for wastewater services, and the piloting of source-separated systems within urban wastewater jurisdictions could support the uptake. Understanding these regulations and adapting to them can be crucial for businesses aiming to implement novel sanitation.

4. Stakeholder engagement process

Stakeholder engagement (SE) is a complex but essential component of contemporary governance and organizational practice. The methodologies for engaging stakeholders are diverse, ranging from structured frameworks to more participatory approaches that emphasize dialogue and co-creation. However, the practice of stakeholder engagement is not without its challenges, including power imbalances, conflicting interests, and the need to balance inclusivity with efficiency. Understanding these challenges and the theoretical foundations of stakeholder engagement is crucial for developing effective strategies that ensure meaningful participation and contribute to more informed and sustainable decision-making (Reed et al., 2009).

During P2Green SE activities a community-led and co-creation approach was followed. The SE process aimed to develop a set of community-led strategies to facilitate the process of engaging with local stakeholders and assist partners to develop the regional stakeholder network, which is required to operationalise P2Green's innovative systems solutions, so that P2Green creates the required wider impact across its pilot regions. For example, Norström et al. (2020) articulate an "iterative and collaborative processes involving diverse types of expertise, knowledge and actors to produce context-specific knowledge and pathways towards a sustainable future" (p. 183). Special focus is put on the importance of contextualized, interactive, and action-based stakeholder engagement (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Principles for knowledge co-production in sustainability research (Norström et al., 2020)

4.1 Overview and objectives

Withing P2Green, Task T4.2 aims to co-create strategies to empower and engage local businesses and relevant stakeholders. The task runs throughout the whole project from M1 to M48. Based on the outcomes of T4.2, this deliverable includes stakeholder engagement strategies based on co-developed and community-led strategies to facilitate the process of engaging with local stakeholders and assist partners in developing the regional stakeholder network. This deliverable provides guidelines for crafting and adapting the 'core message' to drive interests of various tentative public, private and business partners.

The fundamental steps of the strategies co-creation process are based on the following objectives:

- Develop an understanding of the specific national and regional contexts of N&P recovery for each pilot region.
- Map and develop an understanding of relevant stakeholders in the national and regional context of N&P recovery for each pilot and follower region.
- Co-develop community-led strategies to facilitate the process of engaging with local stakeholders to assist partners to develop the regional stakeholder network and operationalise P2Green's innovative system solutions to increase impact across the pilot regions.
 - Identify and map stakeholders involved in the pilot regions according to their sectors and areas of expertise in N&P recovery.
 - Identify the pressing needs, challenges and potential benefits according to the stakeholders' profiles.
 - Define actions for engagement.

4.2 Methodology

The methodology for the SE process was adapted based on established approaches in the academic literature (Greenwood, 2007; Ray & Miller, 2017; Gould, 2012; Iazzi et al., 2020; Bourne, 2016; Li & Feng, 2021; Bruce-Iri & Shelley, 2010; Stocker Arruda et al., 2018) and has been tested in practice through other EU projects. The relevance of knowledge co-production in the SE process, as outlined by Norström et al. (2020), was taken into consideration (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Stakeholder engagement method

The SE process was structured by the concrete activities, which were shared with the project partners to keep an overview and inform the process throughout:

- Map (WS1)

In the initial phase of the SE process, stakeholders were systematically mapped and ranked based on their field and level of operation, affiliation to pilot and follower regions as well as relevance. All stakeholders were listed in a stakeholder database file (later shared with T5.1 and incorporated in P2Green's Network hub).

- Gain Overview (WS 1)

Following the mapping exercise, a comprehensive analysis of stakeholders was conducted. Stakeholders were categorized based on types, their importance was assessed, and their reach was determined. Results were organized into a spreadsheet and visually represented for clarity. Subsequently, each pilot region was asked to reach out to the identified stakeholders and started to identify potential participants in the following workshops (WS2).

- Activate (WS2)

The activation phase focused on understanding the local context and stakeholder landscape of each pilot region (WS2). This phase aimed to identify challenges and needs specific to each stakeholder, enabling the prioritization of efforts in each region, setting the stage for a more targeted approach. During this process, identification of stakeholders interested in specific activities and assessment of their potential contributions also took place.

- Strategize (WS3)

Moving into the strategize phase, collaboration with stakeholders in Workshops (WS3) occurred to co-design strategies to engage local stakeholders, to tackle the specific challenges identified in the previous workshops. Additionally, the focus was set on challenges and potential solutions to difficulties in stakeholder engagement and management were addressed. This workshop led to co-developed community engagement strategies and stakeholder engagement calendars to be carried out through the project timeline.

- Execute (Dissemination of co-developed strategies)

With a well-defined engagement plan and co-developed strategies, the development of pilot-specific dissemination materials (videos, flyers, informational material) was carried out. Here a close collaboration with WP6 took place to develop the campaigns and materials to be used across various media.

- Evaluate (Feedback survey)

During the first evaluation phase, a feedback survey was conducted. Highlighting feedback on the applied methodology and potential improvements to be continuously implemented in T4.2's activities. The evaluation will be continued until the end of the project in M48.

One of the key concepts utilized for the SE in P2Green is the concept of co-creation, which revolves around fostering collaborative partnerships and active involvement of stakeholders within the decision-making as well as the solution-building process. Co-creation emphasizes a departure from traditional top-down approaches, encouraging an inclusive environment where stakeholders contribute their insights, expertise, and perspectives. This collaborative process acknowledges that stakeholders bring unique knowledge and experiences to the table, making them essential co-creators of value. By engaging stakeholders in workshops, brainstorming sessions, and participatory activities, one does not only foster effective solutions but also cultivates a sense of ownership and commitment among stakeholders. Co-creation in stakeholder engagement is about recognizing the mutual benefits derived from shared responsibility and jointly shaping outcomes to address the diverse needs and aspirations of all involved parties. Additionally, co-creation aims to identify key

challenges and relevant topics for each stakeholder to develop specific strategies and indicators to act upon to achieve these defined objectives. Additionally, the engagement was focused on the co-production of tangible results. This was achieved by going beyond the generation of ideas and extending it with the collaborative execution of plans, with stakeholders playing a vital role in bringing solutions to life, highlighting the practical and operational dimensions of stakeholder involvement in the overall process (Greenwood, 2007; Ray & Miller, 2017; Gould, 2012; Iazzi et al., 2020; Bourne, 2016; Li & Feng, 2021; Bruce-Iri & Shelley, 2010; Stocker, Arruda et al., 2018).

4.3 Stakeholder Mapping and Overview: WS1 - Initial stakeholder mapping

The initial stakeholder engagement mapping took place during the first consortium meeting (COM) on the 12th of January 2023 (see appendix A; A.1). All project partners were invited to participate based on their affiliation to one of the pilot or follower regions. Therefore, three exercises for the pilot regions and four for the following regions took place simultaneously. The workshop engaged all present consortium members across work packages. All exercises were designed identically to have comparable outcomes. Main objectives of WS1:

1. Present the stakeholder engagement process.
2. Map stakeholders relevant to the pilot and follower regions.
3. Facilitate an open discussion and cross-collaboration among project partners about stakeholders relevant to the project.

WS1 - Meetings and materials

In the following table, WS 1 and all affiliated meetings are listed. Additionally, regular WP4 meetings were used to present and discuss developments (see Table 1).

Workshop and meetings	Content	N Participants	Date
Initial stakeholder mapping workshop (WS1)	Introduction to stakeholder engagement. Mapping and ranking of relevant stakeholders for all pilot and follower regions	49	12th of January 2023; 14.30 – 16.00
Feedback meeting and next steps	Monthly WP4 meeting: feedback from WS1. Presentation of reporting and planning of next steps.	29	13 th of February 2023; 15.30 – 16.30
Stakeholder database	Collaborative meeting with T5.1 to integrate the stakeholder base into the P2Green network hub	6	17 th of May 2023; 11.30 – 12.00

Table 1: Meetings WS1

WS1 - Method and tools

For the workshop, which was planned to comprise 1.5 hours the participants had to brainstorm, map, and rank relevant stakeholders in their pilot region. All participants were encouraged to discuss, align, and complement the results of the exercises.

The participants were asked to map stakeholders based on their area and level of operation to create a preliminary categorization of actors and their level of operation:

Area of operation

- **Public authorities:** Entities established by the government to serve the public interest and are created by the legislature. They may possess varying degrees of independence from the state, depending on the authority granted to them by their legislative mandate, which includes both powers and limitations.
- **SME/ businesses:** In the European Union, 99% of businesses are classified as small or medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). This category encompasses a wide range of business sizes and types, ranging from sole proprietorships to enterprises with hundreds of staff and refers to private operating businesses.
- **Research/ academia:** This category refers to all stakeholders operating in research projects, academia or universities.
- **NGOs:** Non-governmental organisation (NGO) functions autonomously and are typically focused on addressing social or political issues within a specific scope.
- **General public:** Stakeholders within this category are defined as individuals or groups within society that may be of interest for project partners and interested in the project outcomes.
- **Others:** This category gives the option to list other stakeholder that may not fit into one of the earlier listed categories. However, with further analysis this section will be fed into the other categories.

Level of operation

- **Local/Regional level:** Stakeholders operating in a geographically and operationally limited area mostly focusing on local and regional topics.
- **National level:** Stakeholders operating on government or federal government level are mostly focusing on national topics or inter-governmental topics.
- **International/European level:** Stakeholders operating above state level are mostly focusing on global, European, or collaborative approaches with other international players.
- The three layers represent the multi-level governance and operation formation that is expected among the listed stakeholders.

1st Exercise – Brainstorming

In the first exercise, participants were asked to brainstorm and list all stakeholders relevant for their pilot region. The partners were asked to categorise the stakeholders according to the level of operation (local/regional, national, international) and their operation area (public authorities, SMEs and businesses, research/ academia, NGOs, General public and others). The brainstorming table developed specifically for the task by CBS supported the exercise (Figure 3).

Stakeholder mapping

	Public authorities	SMEs and businesses	Research/academic	NGOs	General public	Others
Local/regional level						
National level						
European level						

Figure 3: 1st Exercise: Initial stakeholder mapping. WS1

2nd Exercise – Relevance ranking

In the second exercise, the partners were asked to rank the mapped stakeholders from exercise 1 according to their relevance in the local project context. The stakeholders were ranked in low, medium and high relevance within the identified operation area and context of the pilot region (Figure 4).

Relevance mapping

	Public Authorities	SMEs and businesses	Research/academic	NGOs	General public	Others
High relevance						
Medium relevance						
Low relevance						

Figure 4: 2nd Exercise: Stakeholder relevance mapping. WS 1

The activities were developed by CBS based on the tools and canvases presented by Mastrogiacomo and Osterwalder (2021).

WS1 - Reports and analysis

The following section will present the outcomes of the first stakeholder mapping workshop (WS1). This initial mapping functions as a base to create a stakeholder database indicating relevant stakeholders in the pilot areas. Here not only individual listed actors are of interest, but also categories of stakeholders. The analysis of stakeholders (categories) functions as a map of actors with whom to engage and invite to the next steps and workshops of the project. The outcomes of the workshop comprise an overview of stakeholders clustered by pilot and follower region. Furthermore, a relevance ranking combined with a contact overview of the listed stakeholders was carried out to show the importance of single actors and stakeholder categories for the project and facilitate the following communication and subsequent interactions.

Germany

For the German pilot overall 72 actors have been listed. 27 are listed within local or regional level, 24 on national and 21 actors are operating on international/ European level. 25 actors are listed with high relevance, 24 with medium 23 with low relevance across all areas of operation. The following visual illustrates the mapped stakeholders in the German pilot region according to their relevancy and level (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Overview of all mapped stakeholders in the German pilot. WS1

Local regional:

Figure 6 presents the overview of stakeholders mapped on local and regional levels in the German pilot.

Figure 6: Stakeholders Germany on local/ regional level. WS1

Within the local and regional scope (27 actors) the three main areas of operations are public authorities (41%), SMEs and business (22%) and General public (18%).

Municipalities and especially municipal wastewater authorities are listed among the public authorities potentially of interest and relevant for the pilot regions. Furthermore, municipal buildings and local building authorities are mapped. Federal county authorities (environmental, construction, and climate protection departments) are listed as well as wastewater associations and construction authorities.

Within the local/ regional level, 10 stakeholders with high relevancy have been listed (see Table 2: Highly relevant Stakeholders on local/ regional level in Germany. WS1Table 2).

Name	Function	Description
Municipal wastewater authorities	Public authority	In Germany, the responsibility for public wastewater disposal lies with the government, which is carried out by municipalities and cities as part of their public duties. The German wastewater sector is highly fragmented, with almost 7,000 local authority wastewater management entities, which are relatively small.
Chamber of Agriculture (Landwirtschaftskammer)/ Landwirtschaftskammer Düngemittel Behörde)	Public authority	The area of responsibility of the Chamber of Agriculture extends to the care and promotion of agricultural professionals. It ensures that agricultural businesses operate profitably, in an environmentally friendly and consumer-friendly manner, and produce corresponding products. In addition, it promotes the professional and social interests of the workforce and ensures the further development of agricultural vocational training.
Building authority	Public authority	The building authority takes over the building activity of the respective body as a fiscal activity in different formats, e.g. B. building construction (schools, administration buildings) or civil engineering (road construction, canal construction) of a community. Furthermore, building authorities are responsible for municipal land use planning.

Country authorities (environmental/ construction)	Public authority	Authorities such as environmental or construction agencies, operating on a district level.
Vendors of fertilizer	SME/ business	The German market is supplied by various fertilizer production and vending companies.
Farmers	SME/ business	Different-sized farms operating in different scopes.
Compost systems	SME/ business	Know-how supplier in biological waste treatment. Focus on recycling organic raw materials, supplying efficient engineering and products for the mechanical and biological treatment of a wide variety of waste streams. The companies' services contribute to conserving resources and groundwater, reducing emissions, and increasing efficiency in our ecosystem.
Finizio	SME/ business	The company provides various sanitary systems for different sites to recover soil out of human excrement.
PTC	SME/ business	PTC provides digital solutions to help companies optimize operations, improve product development, and enhance business performance through technologies like the Internet of Things (IoT), augmented reality (AR), computer-aided design (CAD), and product lifecycle management (PLM).

Table 2: Highly relevant Stakeholders on local/ regional level in Germany. WS1

National level:

Figure 7 presents the overview of German stakeholders mapped on national level.

Figure 7: Stakeholders Germany on national level. WS1

On national level, 24 actors are listed while 29% are mapped as NGOs and 29% as Research/ academia. 13% of actors are operating as SMEs/ businesses and further 13% of mapped stakeholders are affiliated to public authorities. Within research and academia stakeholders such as research institutes, relevant EU projects, and scientific associations are listed. Additionally, relevant NGOs have also been mapped. As public authorities, the Ministry of agriculture and Environment as well as the Federal Environmental Agency are listed. Additionally, standardisation bodies such as the DIN are mentioned.

On national level 8 highly relevant stakeholders are identified (see Table 3).

Name	Function	Description
Ministry for Agriculture/ Environment (BMLE/BMUV)	Public authority	Ministry operating on national level focusing on food security, animal husbandry labelling, organic farming, biodiversity, food and nutrition strategy and climate stewardship. Further the focus is on Chemicals, Resources, Waste and sustainability.
Federal Environmental Agency (Umweltbundesamt) (data on soil)	Public authority	The agency is a central environmental authority, which ensures that Germany has a healthy environment in which people can live protected as far as possible from harmful environmental influences, such as pollutants in the air or water. The range of topics is wide - from waste avoidance to the climate protection until the approval of plant protection products.
RAL (for compost)	SME/ business	The quality seal comprises permissible raw materials, product definition, quality requirements and quality control for compost for use as a soil improver and fertilizer as well as requirements for the process quality, the goods declaration and the proper use of the products.
Scientific assessments	SME/ business	The association promotes scientific and technical research and development projects both in the field of urban building naturalization, including the necessary production of plant material in intra- and peri-urban agriculture, as well as in the field of food management for animal health, the recycling of biogenic waste and consumer and environmental protection.
NetSan	NGO	NetSan eV is a collaborative network consisting of diverse participants aiming to achieve a sustainable and eco-friendly sanitation and nutrient transition. This community comprises individuals from various fields such as science, research, start-ups, small and medium-sized companies who come together to share knowledge, network, and collaborate on innovative projects related to the responsible management of human waste, while also focusing on climate sustainability.
Research Association (Leibniz network)	NGO	The Leibniz Association connects 97 independent research institutions that range in focus from natural, engineering, and environmental sciences to economics, spatial and social sciences, and the humanities. Leibniz Institutes address issues of social, economic, and ecological relevance.
Global public and private users	General public	Key stakeholders for broad dissemination, demand, and acceptance.

Table 3: Highly relevant Stakeholders on national level in Germany. WS1

International/ European level:

Figure 8 presents the overview of international and European stakeholders in the German pilot.

Figure 8: Stakeholders Germany on international/ European level. WS1

21 actors are listed on international/ European level according to their area of operation 29% of the actors are mapped as NGOs, which comprise environmental and social associations. 19% of the actors are listed as research/ academia and general public. The section “others” represents 14% of the mapped stakeholders. Here, sister projects, influencers, and social media actors are listed.

On European and international level 7 highly relevant stakeholders are identified (see Table 4).

Name	Function	Description
Directorate federal agriculture	Public authority	Development of common agricultural policies, and rural development.
Members of the European Parliament/ Political decision-makers (public authority)	Public authority	Political decision-makers and members of the EU parliament are elected by the member states and form EU politics.
EAWAG	NGO	Focus of research is on drinking and wastewater, ecosystems, biodiversity, societal decision making, and climate change.
Valoo/ RAE	NGO	The Ecological Sanitation Network (RAE) is an association whose objective is to defend the general interest in terms of sanitation. The RAE is part of an approach to preserving the environment through the responsible management of natural resources as well as the prevention and reduction of domestic organic pollution. Collaboration with NetSan.
(EU) sister projects	Others	E.g. ZirkulierBAR project.

Table 4: Highly relevant Stakeholders on international/ European level Germany. WS1

Sweden

For the Swedish pilots overall 60 stakeholders are listed. On a local/ regional level, 19 actors have been mapped, on national, 29 and on international, 12 stakeholders. Overall, 19 stakeholders have been ranked with low relevance in the pilot region. 22 stakeholders are listed with medium relevance and 19 are listed with high relevance.

The following visualisation shows an overview of the mapped stakeholders according to their relevancy and level (see Figure 9).

Figure 9: Overview of all mapped stakeholders in the Swedish pilot. WS1

Local regional level:

Figure 10 shows stakeholders mapped on the regional level in the Swedish pilot.

Figure 10: Stakeholders Sweden on local level. WS1

Within the local level, 19 stakeholders are listed. Within these 19 actors, nearly half (47%) have been identified as SMEs/ businesses, 21% are public authorities and 16% are listed as general public. Research and academia only represent 5%, NGOs 11%, and the general public 16%. No other actors are listed.

On local and regional level, 7 actors are listed as high relevance actors (see Table 5).

Name	Function	Description
Gotland region	Public authority	The administrative body responsible for overseeing public services, healthcare, and regional development in Gotland. Plays a key role in shaping sustainability policies.
Gotland Kommune	Public authority	The local government of Gotland, responsible for municipal services, community planning, and local policy implementation. Works to enhance local sustainability initiatives.
GEAB	SME/ business	Gotland's main energy company, Gotland's Energi AB (GEAB), responsible for electricity distribution and renewable energy projects across the island.
CEMENTA	SME/ business	A major local industrial actor in Gotland, Cementa operates limestone quarries and cement production facilities, contributing significantly to the local economy.
LRF Gotland	SME/ business	The local branch of the Swedish Federation of Farmers (LRF), representing agricultural interests in Gotland and focusing on sustainable farming and rural development.
GAGT	NGO	An association dedicated to promoting sustainable and green practices in Gotland, with a focus on renewable energy, local food production, and community resilience.
P4 Radio	SME/ business	P4 Gotland, part of Sveriges Radio, is a key local radio station providing news and information to residents, playing a role in public awareness on sustainability issues.

Table 5: Highly relevant Stakeholders on local/ regional level Sweden. WS1

National level:

Figure 11 shows the mapped stakeholders on national level in Sweden.

Figure 11: Stakeholders Sweden on national level. WS1

On the national level 29 actors are listed, while 17% represent public authorities, 41% of them are SME/ businesses. 4% represent Research and academia and 31% of the

actors are defined as NGOs. 7% of the stakeholders listed are identified as others. No actors from the general public are listed.

On national level, 11 actors have been defined as highly relevant for the pilot region (see Table 6).

Name	Function	Description
Naturvårdsverket (EPA)	Public authority	Sweden's national environmental protection agency, responsible for sustainable policies.
Hyrtoaletten	SME/ business	Provides rental and service of portable toilets across Sweden.
IKEA	SME/ business	Global furniture and home goods retailer headquartered in Sweden.
PEAB	SME/ business	Large Swedish construction company involved in building and infrastructure projects.
Svensknärings platform	Others	Supports Swedish industry and economic growth through collaboration and policy.
Svenskt Vatten	Public authority	National organization responsible for water and wastewater management in Sweden.
Avfall Sverige	Public authority	National organization for waste management and recycling in Sweden.
KRAV	Public authority	Swedish certification agency for organic food and farming practices.
Orientering National Club	NGO	Swedish orienteering club promoting outdoor activities and nature navigation sports.
SVT/Sveriges Radio	SME/ business	Sweden's national public television (SVT) and radio (Sveriges Radio) broadcasters.
LRF Gotland	SME/ business	Local division of the Federation of Swedish Farmers, promoting sustainable agriculture.

Table 6: Highly relevant Stakeholders on national level in Sweden. WS1

International/ European level:

Figure 12 shows the mapped stakeholders operating on international and European level in Sweden.

Figure 12: Stakeholders Sweden on international/ European level. WS1

On international level 12 stakeholders have been identified. 33% of them are affiliated as NGOs and 34% as SMEs/ businesses and NGOs. 25% are listed as public authority. 8% are listed as others and no actors from the general public were listed.

None of the stakeholders on international level are listed as highly important. However, 7 actors are listed as medium important (see Table 7).

Name	Function	Description
Horizon Europe	Public authority	The EU's key funding program for research and innovation, focusing on green and digital transitions.
European Investment Bank (EIB)	Public authority	The EU's bank providing finance and expertise for sustainable development projects globally.
Fertiliser Company	SME/ business	An international company that provides fertilizers and agricultural products.
European P Platform	Others	A European network focusing on phosphorus sustainability, recycling, and resource management.
Organic Farming Europe	NGO	A European association promoting organic farming, sustainable food production, and policy development.
Baltic Sea Action Plan	Others	A regional agreement focused on improving the ecological state of the Baltic Sea through sustainable practices.
Angel Investors	SME/ business	Private individuals or groups providing financial support to start-ups, particularly in sustainable sectors.

Table 7: Highly relevant Stakeholders on international/ European level in Sweden. WS1

Spain

In the Spanish pilot overall 41 stakeholders are listed. On a local/ regional level, 19 actors are mapped, on national level, 10 and on international level, 12 stakeholders. Overall, 19 stakeholders are listed with high relevance, 12, medium and 10, low relevance. The following visualisation shows an overview of the mapped stakeholders according to their relevancy and level (see Figure 13).

Figure 13: Overview of all mapped stakeholders in the Spanish pilot. WS1

Local regional:

Figure 14 shows the stakeholders listed on local and regional level in Spain.

Figure 14: Stakeholders Spain on local/ regional level. WS1

Among the listed 19 actors within the local and regional scope in the Spanish pilot, NGOs account for 32% of the actors. Within this group of stakeholders such as Junta de Analucia, Municipality of Algorrobo, Mancomunidad, Duoytación Málaga,

Mediterranean River basin are listed. Additionally, public authorities make up 26% of the total ones listed. These are governmental bodies, municipalities, and other public institutions involved in decision-making. 13% of actors are operating as SMEs/ businesses and other 13% of mapped stakeholders are affiliated to research/academia, the general public constitutes 10% of the actors.

Within the local/ regional level 11 stakeholders with high relevancy are listed (see Table 8).

Name	Function	Description
Junta de Andalucía	Public authority	The Junta de Andalucía is a public authority in Spain with various functions and responsibilities. It is the regional government of the autonomous community of Andalusia, one of the seventeen autonomous communities in Spain. The Junta de Andalucía operates as an administrative body and exercises executive, legislative, and regulatory functions within its jurisdiction.
Municipality of Algarrobo	Public authority	The Municipality of Algarrobo is a local public authority located in Spain. Situated within the province of Málaga, in the autonomous community of Andalusia, the municipality serves as the governing body for the town of Algarrobo and its surrounding areas.
Crops selling companies	SME/ business	Crops-selling companies in Spain, operating as SMEs or businesses, play a significant role in the agricultural sector and the overall food supply chain. These companies specialize in the sale and distribution of crops, acting as intermediaries between farmers and buyers, and offering various functions and services within their operations.
CSIC - La Mayora	Research/ academia	CSIC - La Mayora, a research institution affiliated with the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), is known for its expertise in the field of agricultural research. Located in Spain, CSIC - La Mayora conducts scientific studies and provides valuable contributions to the agricultural sector.
University of Malaga	Research/ academia	The University of Malaga is a prominent research and academic institution located in Spain. It serves as a hub for knowledge creation, innovation, and educational excellence.
Subtropical crops association	NGO	The Subtropical Crops Association is a non-governmental organization (NGO) in Spain that focuses on the promotion, research, and sustainable development of subtropical crops.
Irrigation communities	NGO	Irrigation communities in Spain, as NGOs, play a critical role in managing and operating irrigation systems. These organizations serve as important pillars in ensuring sustainable irrigation practices and the equitable distribution of water resources among farmers.
Local development groups	NGO	Local development groups in Spain, as NGOs, play a significant role in facilitating the recovery and sustainable management of N&P.
Crop cooperatives	NGO	Crop cooperatives in Spain, as NGOs, serve as important entities in the agricultural sector, representing the interests of farmers and promoting their collective well-being.
Farmers	General public	Different-sized farms operating in different scopes.
Consumers	General public	Key stakeholders for broad dissemination, demand, and acceptance.

Table 8: Highly relevant Stakeholders on regional/ local level in Spain. WS1

National level:

Figure 15 shows national stakeholders in the Spanish pilot.

Figure 15: Stakeholders Spain on national level. WS1

At the national level, there are 10 actors included in the mapping. Among them, the largest group of mapped stakeholders is public authorities, 30% of the total actors. Research/academia, SMEs/businesses, and the general public each account for 20% of the mapped stakeholders. Additionally, the category labelled "others" that represents 10% of the stakeholders, the organization Innovai IRV, a technical innovation centre applied to industry is listed. Notably, NGOs are not listed in this mapping.

On national level, 4 highly relevant stakeholders have been identified (see Table 9).

Name	Function	Description
Crops selling companies	SME/ business	Crops selling companies in Spain, operating as SMEs or businesses, play a significant role in the agricultural sector and the overall food supply chain. These companies specialize in the sale and distribution of crops, acting as intermediaries between farmers and buyers, and offering various functions and services within their operations.
Smart agriculture companies	SME/ business	Smart agriculture companies in Spain, operating at the national level as SMEs, play a significant role in leveraging technology and innovation to optimize agricultural practices and promote sustainable farming.
Farmers	General public	Different sized farms operating in different scopes.
Consumers	General public	Key stakeholders for broad dissemination, demand and acceptance.

Table 9: Highly relevant Stakeholders on national level in Spain. WS1

International/ European level:

Figure 16 shows international and European stakeholders in Spain.

Figure 16: Stakeholders Spain on international/ European level. WS1

On the international/European level, the mapping includes 12 actors based on their area of operation. Among the main actors, 41% are categorized as research/academia. The listed actors in this category include EIP-WATER (European Innovation Partnership on Water), WIRE Action Group (water and irrigated agriculture), Circular Economy Industry Platform, EIP-AGRI (Agricultural European Innovation Partnership), and EIT (European Institute of Innovation and Technology). Public authorities represent 25% of the actors listed in the mapping. Both SMEs/businesses and the general public are represented by 17% of the mapped stakeholders each. It's important to note that the specific NGOs are not included in this mapping.

On European and international level 4 highly relevant stakeholders have been identified (Table 10).

Name	Function	Description
Crop selling and distribution industry	SME/ business	Development of common agricultural policies, rural development.
EIP - WATER (European Innovation Partnership on Water)	Research/ academia	The European Innovation Partnership on Water (EIP-Water) serves as a platform for promoting collaboration and innovation in the water sector across Europe. It brings together stakeholders from various backgrounds, including research institutions, industry, public authorities, NGOs, and end-users, to address water-related challenges and drive sustainable solutions.
Farmers	General public	Different sized farms operating in different scopes.
Consumers	General public	Key stakeholders for broad dissemination, demand and acceptance.

Table 10: Highly relevant Stakeholders on international/ European level in Spain. WS1

Greece

In the Greece pilot region, overall, 33 stakeholders are listed. On local/ regional level 6 stakeholders have been identified. Most of the stakeholders listed, 18 actors, are operating on national level and 9 on international/ European level. Overall, 10 stakeholders are listed with high relevance, 16 with medium relevance, and 7 with low relevancy. The following figure shows the overview of stakeholders on all levels and within all relevancies (see Figure 17).

Figure 17: Overview of all mapped stakeholders in the Greek pilot. WS1

Local/ regional level:

Figure 18 shows local and regional stakeholders in Greece.

Figure 18: Stakeholders Greece on local/regional level. WS1

On local/ regional level, overall, 6 stakeholders are identified. 33% are affiliated with public authorities as well as SME/ businesses. NGOs and the general public are each represented with 17%. No actors were identified as others. On local/ regional level 5 stakeholders are mapped with high relevancy (see Table 11).

Name	Function	Description
Karditsa Municipality	Public authority	Responsible for local governance, urban planning, and implementing agricultural policies in Karditsa.
Ministry of Agriculture	Public authority	Oversees national agricultural policies, programs, and initiatives related to sustainable development.
Metropolitan Expo	SME/businesses	Organizes exhibitions and events focusing on sustainability, agriculture, and local development in the region.
Southern Lights	NGO	Promotes and develops renewable energy projects in the Southern Greece region, focusing on community engagement.
Co-operative of Nikaia	SME/ businesses	A local cooperative that supports farmers in Nikaia, promoting sustainable practices and community support.
Breweries/ microbreweries	SME/ businesses	Local microbreweries as interested stakeholders in P2Green solutions.

Table 11: Highly relevant Stakeholders on regional/ local level in Greece. WS1

National level:

Figure 19 shows national stakeholders in the Greek pilot.

Figure 19: Stakeholders Greece on national level. WS1

44% of the 18 listed stakeholders, operating on national level are SMEs/ businesses. Public authorities as well as Research and academia make up 17% each. NGOs and others are represented by 11% each. Four actors with high relevancy are listed (Table 12).

Name	Function	Description
Ministry of Agriculture	Public authority	Responsible for formulating and implementing agricultural policies,

		supporting farmers, and ensuring food security.
EENE - National boy of inspection	Public authority	Oversees compliance with agricultural and food safety standards, conducting inspections and enforcing regulations.
EYDAP - national water company	Public authority	Provides water supply and wastewater treatment services in Athens, focusing on sustainable water management practices.
Certification authorities	Public authority	Grant certifications for organic farming and sustainable practices, ensuring compliance with national and international standards.

Table 12: Highly relevant Stakeholders on national level in Greece. WS1

European level:

Figure 20 shows stakeholders on international and European level in Greece.

Figure 20: Stakeholders Greece on international/ EU level. WS1

In international level, 9 stakeholders are listed. 11% are listed as public authorities. 34% of the listed stakeholders are SMEs/ businesses, another 33% are the general public and 22% are others, such as the two companies AgroFossil Free and Bio Rural. No other stakeholders were listed. The company Bio Rural is also listed as highly relevant stakeholder (see Table 13).

Name	Function	Description
BioRural	Others	The BioRural project aims to integrate small-scale bio-based solutions into European rural areas to promote sustainable bioeconomy practices, increase rural development, and establish a network for knowledge exchange and innovation.

Table 13: Highly relevant Stakeholders on international/ European level in Greece. WS1

Hungary

There were identified a total of 31 stakeholders at the Hungarian pilot project. These stakeholders are distributed across different levels: 15 at the local/regional level, 10 at the national level, and 6 at the international level. Among these stakeholders, 6 are considered highly relevant, 12 have medium relevance, and 13 have low relevance across all operational areas. The following visual representation depicts the stakeholders in the Hungarian pilot region, categorized according to their level and relevance (see Figure 21).

Figure 21: Overview of all mapped stakeholders in Hungarian pilot. WS1

Local regional:

Figure 22 shows local and regional stakeholders in Hungary.

Figure 22: Stakeholders Hungary on local/ regional level. WS1

In the local and regional context, the main focus of operations involves SMEs/businesses, accounting for 54% of the actors identified. Among the businesses listed as potentially interested and relevant for the pilot regions, local farmers and Noragro Ltd stand out. Public authorities, NGOs, and a group labelled as *Others* each make up 13% of the actors included in the mapping. This category includes secondary schools for agriculture and dormitories. Research and academia represent 7% of the actors listed. It is worth noting that the general public is not included in this specific mapping.

Within the local/ regional level 5 stakeholders with high relevancy are listed (see Table 14).

Name	Function	Description
Local waste treatment company NON-Authority	Public authority	Manages waste collection and treatment services in the region, ensuring compliance with environmental regulations.
Local farmers	SME/ business	Engage in agricultural production, contributing to local food supply and promoting sustainable farming practices.
Noragro Ltd agricultural sites	SME/ business	Provides agricultural products and services, focusing on sustainable practices and innovation in farming.
Camping sites	SME/ business	Offer accommodation services, promoting eco-tourism and sustainable practices in their operations.
Public/ festivals toilet rentals	SME/ business	Provide portable toilet solutions for events and festivals, focusing on sustainability and sanitation standards.

Table 14: Highly relevant Stakeholders on local/ regional level in Hungary. WS1

National level:

Figure 23 shows national stakeholders in Hungary.

Figure 23: Stakeholders Hungary on national level. WS1

At the national level of the Hungarian pilot region, a total of 10 stakeholders are listed. Among these stakeholders, 40% are categorized under Research/Academia. This group includes research institutes, relevant EU projects, and scientific associations. Public authorities account for the second largest group, representing 30% of the listed actors. The Ministry of Agriculture and the NÉBIH National Food Security Authority are

specifically listed. NGOs, SMEs/businesses, and a category labelled as "Others" each constitute 10% of the actors included in the mapping. It should be noted that the general public is not considered in this particular mapping. No general public was listed. On national level 4 stakeholders with higher level of relevance have been identified (see Table 15).

Name	Function	Description
NÉBIH National Food security authority	Public authority	Responsible for food safety, security, and quality in Hungary, ensuring compliance with national and EU standards.
Ministry for agriculture	Public authority	Oversees agricultural policy, promoting sustainable practices, food security, and rural development in Hungary.
University of Pannonia	Research/ academia	Engages in agricultural and environmental research, providing education and expertise on sustainable practices.
Gourmet Festival	SME/ business	Promotes local gastronomy and food culture, local producers and sustainable food practices through events.

Table 15: Highly relevant Stakeholders on national level in Hungary. WS1

International/ European level:

Figure 24 shows international and European stakeholders in Hungary.

Figure 24: Stakeholders Hungary on international/ European level. WS1

At the international/European level, a total of 6 actors are listed based on their areas of operation. Among these actors, two main groups emerge: Public authorities and NGOs, each representing 33% of the mapped stakeholders. Additionally, 17% of the stakeholders are categorized as research/academia. The "Others" section accounts for another 17% of the mapped stakeholders, with notable inclusion of the Sziget Festival. Neither SME/businesses nor general public were listed. On European and international level 1 highly relevant stakeholder is identified as Covenant of mayors (NGOs) (see Table 16).

Name	Function	Description
Covenant of mayors	NGO	A European initiative that brings together local governments voluntarily committing to increasing energy efficiency and the use of renewable energy sources in their territories. The

		covenant promotes sustainable urban development and helps municipalities take action against climate change.
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Table 16: Highly relevant Stakeholders on international/ European level in Hungary. WS1

Italy

In the Italian pilot overall 25 stakeholders are listed. On a local/ regional level, 6 actors are mapped, on national, 11 and on international, 8 stakeholders. Overall, 7 stakeholders are listed with high relevance, 7, medium and 11, low relevance across all operational areas. The following visual representation depicts the stakeholders in the Italian pilot region, categorized according to their level and relevance (see Figure 25).

Figure 25: Overview of all mapped stakeholders in Italian pilot. WS1

Local regional:

Figure 26 shows stakeholders on local and regional level in Italy.

Figure 26: Stakeholders Italy on local/ regional level. WS1

In the local and regional context, there has been a total of 6 actors identified, with the main area of operations being public authorities, representing 50% of the mapped stakeholders. Among the listed public authorities that are potentially interested and relevant for the pilot regions, in particular, municipal water utilities and water authorities stand out. SMEs and businesses account for 33% of the mapped stakeholders, with local farmers and highway stations being listed as examples. Additionally, research and academia make up another 17% of the mapped stakeholders. It is important to note that NGOs, general public and others were not listed in this specific mapping.

Within the local/ regional level 2 stakeholders with high relevancy are listed (Table 17).

Name	Function	Description
Finagricola	SME/ business	Finagricola is a small to medium-sized enterprise engaged in agricultural production, specializing in sustainable farming practices and local food supply. They focus on environmentally friendly methods to enhance crop yield while preserving biodiversity.
Cremonini Group- Chef Express	SME/ business	The Cremonini Group operates Chef Express, a dining service at highway stations that provides quality food options. They emphasize sourcing local ingredients and sustainable food practices to enhance the travel experience for customers.

Table 17: Highly relevant Stakeholders on local/ regional level in Italy. WS1

National level:

Figure 27 shows national stakeholders in Italy.

Figure 27: Stakeholders Italy on national level. WS1

At the national level, a total of 11 actors are listed in the mapping. Among these actors, 28% are categorized as public authorities, with the Ministry of Agriculture and the Ministry of Environment specifically mentioned. Research and academia account for 27% of the mapped stakeholders, including research institutes, relevant EU projects, and scientific associations. Additionally, 18% of the stakeholders are classified as NGOs. SMEs and businesses, the general public, and a group labelled as "Others" each represent 9% of the mapped stakeholders. Notably, the "Others" section includes relevant alpine clubs.

On national level 5 highly relevant stakeholders have been identified (see Table 18).

Name	Function	Description
Ministry of Agriculture (MIASAF)	Public authority	The Ministry of Agriculture (MIASAF) oversees agricultural policy and regulation in the country, focusing on sustainable farming practices, food security, and environmental protection.
Assofertilizzanti	SME/ business	An association representing fertilizer manufacturers in Italy, advocating for sustainable fertilization practices and innovation in the agricultural sector.
Association of biofertilizers (ICAS International, Fertileva, Fertil, Agribios Italiana, Green MAS)	Research/ academia	This consortium of organizations promotes the use of biofertilizers and sustainable agriculture, conducting research and providing education on the benefits of organic fertilization methods.
Farmer Associations (Confagricoltura, Coldiretti)	Research/ academia	Prominent farmer associations in Italy, representing the interests of farmers and promoting sustainable agricultural practices and policies.
Highway users	General public	Highway users include all individuals and vehicles utilizing the highway system, impacting traffic, environmental concerns, and the need for sustainable transport solutions.

Table 18: Highly relevant Stakeholders on national level in Italy. WS1

International/ European level:

Figure 28 shows international and European stakeholders.

Figure 28: Stakeholders Italy on international/ European level. WS1

On the international/European level, there are a total of 8 listed actors based on their area of operation. Among these actors, 50% are categorized as SMEs and businesses. Notable inclusions within this category are international fertilizer associations and the European Sustainable Phosphorus Platform. Public authorities and NGOs each represent 25% of the mapped stakeholders. Specifically, the European Research Executive Agency, municipalities, and Directorates-General Environment Commission department are listed as public authorities. It is important to note that research and academia, as well as the general public, were not listed.

On European and international level no highly relevant stakeholders were listed. 3 medium relevant stakeholders have been identified (see Table 19).

Name	Function	Description
COPA- Cogeca (EU Farmers - agro-cooperation)	SME/ business	European farmers and agricultural cooperative, advocating for policies that support sustainable agriculture and rural development at the EU level.
IFA (international fertilizer association)	SME/ business	A global industry association representing fertilizer producers and distributors, focusing on the sustainable use of fertilizers and promoting best practices in nutrient management.
ESPP (European Sustainable Phosphorus Platform)	SME/ business	A multi-stakeholder platform aimed at promoting sustainable phosphorus management in Europe, advocating for resource efficiency and environmental protection in agriculture.

Table 19: Highly relevant Stakeholders on international/ European level in Italy. WS1

France

In the French pilot region, 39 stakeholders have been mapped. Most actors (21) are operating on local/ regional level. Further 13 stakeholders are listed on national level and 5 actors are listed on international/ European level. Overall, 19 stakeholders are listed with high relevance, 17 on medium, and only 3 on low relevance. The overall landscape of stakeholders in the French pilot is illustrated below (see Figure 29).

Figure 29: Overview of all mapped stakeholders in French pilot. WS1

Regional/ local level:

Figure 30 shows local and regional stakeholders in France.

Figure 30: Stakeholders France local/ regional level. WS1

21 stakeholders are listed on local/ regional level of which 38% are categorized as public authorities, 19% as SMEs/ businesses as well as 19% as general public. Within this category neighbourhood councils, volunteers, district managers and building owners are listed.

Out of the 21 stakeholders 12 have been ranked with high relevance (see Table 20).

Name	Function	Description
City of Paris	Public Authority	The local government responsible for managing public services and urban development in Paris.
PEMA	NGO	An organization focused on promoting environmental sustainability and social equity in metropolitan areas.
SiAAP	Public authority	The Syndicat Intercommunal des Eaux d'Île-de-France (SIAAP) oversees water supply and treatment in the region.
Metropole de Grand Paris	Public authority	The metropolitan authority responsible for coordinating urban planning, transportation, and housing in the Greater Paris area.
Public housing offices	Public authority	Local agencies that manage and allocate public housing resources and support affordable housing initiatives.
Water Agency (Seine-Normandy)	Public authority	A regional agency responsible for managing water resources and environmental protection in the Seine-Normandy area.
Plumber companies	SME/ business	Businesses specializing in plumbing services, crucial for maintaining water infrastructure and systems.
CERENA IDF	NGO	An organization dedicated to promoting sustainable practices in the construction and renovation sectors in Île-de-France.
PIREN-Siene	NGO	A research program focused on water quality and management in the Seine River and its tributaries.
Education centres	Research/ academia	Institutions providing training and education on sustainable practices and environmental awareness.

District Manager (St. Vincent De Paul)	NGO	A community organization working to support vulnerable populations through social services and housing assistance.
Building owners of syndicate	SME/ business	A collective of property owners focused on managing shared interests and responsibilities in building maintenance and sustainability efforts.

Table 20: Highly relevant Stakeholders on local/ regional level in France. WS1

National level:

Figure 31 shows national stakeholders in France.

Figure 31: Stakeholders France national level. WS1

On national level, 13 stakeholders are listed of which 38% have been categorised as public authorities and 31% as NGOs. 15% represent SMEs and businesses. Research and academia as well as general public were listed with each 8%. No other stakeholders were listed. Among the listed stakeholders, 5 actors are prioritized (see Table 21).

Name	Function	Description
Ecological Transition Agency (ADEME)	Public authority	The French public agency responsible for promoting ecological transition through initiatives in energy efficiency, waste reduction, and sustainable development.
Ministries (e.g. ecological; health...)	Public authority	Various governmental departments focused on environmental policy, health standards, and sustainable practices across sectors.
Vuna Nexus	NGO	A collaborative platform that facilitates dialogue and partnerships among stakeholders to promote sustainable water management and ecological preservation.
Ecole de Ponts	Research/academia	A prestigious engineering school in France specializing in training professionals in sustainable urban development, infrastructure, and environmental science.
CLCV	NGO	A consumer association focused on promoting housing rights, environmental quality, and sustainable living practices for residents.

Table 21: Highly relevant Stakeholders on national level in France. WS1

International/ European level:

Figure 32 shows international and European stakeholders in France:

Figure 32: Stakeholders France international/ European level. WS1

On international/ European level 5 actors are listed and 40% are categorised as public authorities such as EU offices for dissemination and cities involved in the CCRI. 20% of the stakeholders are listed as SME/businesses as well as research and academia and NGOs (each 20%). The listed business “Laufen” is the only stakeholder listed with high relevance (Table 22).

Name	Function	Description
Laufen	SME/ business	Laufen is a leading manufacturer of sanitary products and solutions, focusing on innovative and sustainable designs for bathrooms and water-saving technologies. They emphasize eco-friendly practices in production and product development.

Table 22: Highly relevant Stakeholders on international/ European level in France. WS1

WS1 - Outcomes

The initial stakeholder mapping (WS1) resulted in the general overview of a large pool of stakeholders for the development and implementation of P2Green. Based on the outcomes, a stakeholder database has been developed. The database provides an overview of how relevant these stakeholders are in relation to the project goals, their field and level of operation, as well as direct contact information. The stakeholder database was shared with the pilots and follower regions as well as T5.1 and it has been incorporated into the P2Green’s network hub. The document has been designed as a live resource and all project partners have been encouraged and committed to complement and update the document regularly.

4.4 Stakeholder Overview and Activation: WS 2 - Stakeholder engagement workshops

The second stakeholder engagement workshops were planned to be carried out in May 2023 (M6) of the project. However, due to organizational reasons and further external project activities the three pilot workshops spread over M6 and M7 (see appendix B; B.1 & B.2). The workshop has been designed to touch upon tasks T4.2, T4.3, and T3.3. to identify current issues and stakeholder contribution within the pilot regions, existing and missing stakeholders' collaboration mechanisms, and overall social acceptance. Therefore, a threefold workshop was co-designed with the project partners ICLEI and IRS, aiming to provide:

- An overview of local stakeholders and their level of participation and engagement to WP4's aim to co-develop community-led strategies to facilitate the process of engaging with local stakeholders and assist partners to develop the regional stakeholder network.
- The mapping of local stakeholders and their individual role functioned as a base for the market assessment, including the analysis of socio-economic contexts in the P2Green pilot regions, assets and obstacles that could empower or restrict businesses from achieving success.
- An overview of existing governance structures among the stakeholders.
- The next steps of the SE activities with the local stakeholders.

WS2 - Meetings and materials

The workshop material comprised of preparation and reporting material and detailed workshop guidelines for the participants which were introduced in an overall preparation meeting with all pilot partners. Additionally, follow-up meetings per pilot, immediately before the workshop were held to prepare the workshop facilitators and clarify any questions related to the workshops (see Table 23).

Overview of affiliated meetings:

Workshop	Content	N Participants	Date & Time	Facilitator
Overall training workshop				
Train the trainers	Workshop to train the pilot leaders and implement the methodology.	36	20 th of March 2023, 10.00 – 11.00	CBS/ collaboration with ICLEI and IRS
Pilot specific training workshops				
Internal workshop: Germany	Internal workshop for clarification and workshop planning	5	13 th of June 2023; 14.00 - 15.00 and 19 th of June 2023; 16.00	CBS
Internal workshop: Sweden	Internal workshop for clarification and workshop planning	8	23 rd of May 2023; 10.00 - 11.00 and 8 th of June; 16.00 – 17.00	CBS
Internal workshop: Spain	Internal workshop for clarification and workshop planning	14	15 th of May 2023; 15.00 – 16.00	CBS
Stakeholder engagement workshops (WS2)				

Workshop with external stakeholders: Germany	WS2 with external stakeholders (online)	13	21 st of June; 10.00 – 13.00	German pilot partners
Workshop with external stakeholders: Sweden	WS2 with external stakeholders (in-person as part of the event “DemoDay”)	25	13 th of June 2023	Swedish pilot partners
Workshop with external stakeholders: Spain	WS2 with external stakeholders (in-person)	44	24 th of May 2023	Spanish pilot partners
Feedback meeting				
Feedback meeting and next steps	Monthly WP4 meeting for feedback from the stakeholder engagement workshops with external partners. Presentation of reporting and planning of next steps	24	10 th of July 2023; 15.30 – 16.30	CBS & ICLEI

Table 23: Meetings WS2

WS2 - Methods and tools

The pilot leaders were responsible for mobilizing the stakeholders formally and informally associated with N&P recovery and further specific technologies tested and implemented in the pilot areas through the channels available, including email messages and online meetings. The mobilization processes were supported by the stakeholder engagement guideline provided by CBS. The workshops were designed to be tailored to specific context, profile of participants, and modes of participation of each event (physical or online).

Stage 1 – Brainstorming

In the first stage, participants had to identify challenges, needs and benefits related to the project activities of P2Green. The brainstorming tool developed specifically for the task by CBS supported the exercise (Figure 33).

Brainstorming key challenges, needs and benefits

How does it work:

- Write down one need, challenge or benefit per post-it and place it on the table. Use different colored post-its for the three columns:

Challenge 1

Challenge 2

Challenge 3

Challenge 4

Challenge 5

Challenge 6

Challenge 7

Challenge 8

Challenge 9

Challenge 10

Challenge 11

Challenge 12

Challenge 13

Challenge 14

Challenge 15

Challenge 16

Challenge 17

Challenge 18

Challenge 19

Challenge 20

- Continue until you can not think of any more challenges, needs or benefits.
- The aim is to get an overview of existing needs, challenges and benefits in the local context.

Description:

"Challenge Statements are intended to provoke perspectives of the unmet need".

- What challenges do you face as a stakeholder in the region? What different perspectives can you see about these challenges?

"Need Statements are about defining what the problem is, without including a solution".

- What is the need of you as a local stakeholder? Do not focus on solutions but the needs that are related to you and your region.

Benefits in participating in the project but also more broadly from nutrient recovery in general.

Challenges	Needs	Benefits

Figure 33: 1st Exercise: Brainstorming on challenges, needs and benefits. WS2

Stage 2 – Relevance assessment

Once the main issues were identified, the participants were invited to rank the issues identified by importance. The ranking process was based on the “Relevance Ranking” template and workshop guidelines according to the high, medium, and low relevance levels (see Figure 33).

Relevance ranking

How does it work:

- Take the identified issues and place them according to their relevance.
- Please identify at least three pressing challenges, needs and benefits

Description:

High relevance: Highly relevant issue that needs to be addressed immediately with special attention. OR highly relevant benefit from the project or nutrient recovery in general.

Medium relevance: Relevant issue that needs to be addressed. OR medium relevant benefit from the project or nutrient recovery in general.

Low relevance: This issue is relevant but not urgent. OR a rather low benefit from the project or nutrient recovery in general.

	Challenges	Needs	Benefits
High relevance			
Medium relevance			
Low relevance			

Figure 34: 2nd Exercise: Relevance ranking. WS2

Stage 3 – Engagement (IN/OUT activity)

At the third stage of the workshop, participants were invited to assess the level of engagement of the stakeholders. The assessment was performed using a Likert scale (with ranks ranging from one to five) on two different moments in time: the current and desired levels of engagement

Figure 35).

Figure 35: 3rd Exercise: In/ Out activity. WS2

All activities were developed by CBS based on the tools and canvases presented by Mastrogiacomo and Osterwalder (2021). Additionally, the workshops comprised an exercise on existing collaboration mechanisms among stakeholders. This exercise was carried out by ICLEI and will be reported in D4.4 At the end of each workshop, IRS held focus group interviews with selected stakeholders. The outcomes of the interviews will be reported in D3.5.

WS2 - Reports and analysis

In the following section, the main WS2 results per pilot workshops are presented.

WS2 - Germany

The German stakeholder engagement workshop was held on the 21st of June 2023 (10.00 - 13.00 o'clock). The workshop comprised 13 participants who participated online. The workshop exercises were translated to German and introduced to the participants online through Miro by the German pilot partners. The workshop was designed as an interactive activity, encouraging the participants to execute the exercises online.

Attendees

A total of 14 participants joined the workshop. Research and academia were represented by 46% and made nearly most participants. Further, 31% were enterprises and 15% of the participants were NGOs. One actor representing a public authority was present (see Figure 36).

Figure 36: Stakeholder present in Germany. WS2

Channels of communication:

- Relevant stakeholders were identified based on the stakeholder database and personal relations to relevant actors.
- The stakeholders considered to join the workshop were reached via personal Email and reminder emails (or phone calls).

Gender dimension:

The workshop had 14 participants, with a gender breakdown of 6 female and 8 male participants. While participants identified within a binary framework (m/f/d), it's important to acknowledge that gender exists on a spectrum and gender diversity, beyond male and female categories, was not explicitly represented or reported in this session. All represented stakeholder areas such as public authorities, SME/ business, NGO, and research/academia were evenly represented. The workshop facilitators are encouraged to foster non-binary as well as gender-diverse participation further to ensure the representation of diverse gender identities.

Identified Challenges, Needs, and Benefits:

The identified **challenges** in the German pilot region include a lack of clarity and safety in the envisioned outcomes of the transformation, as well as difficulties with the certification of fertilizers and the guarantees offered on products. There is a need to ensure acceptance of these fertilizers by farmers, but legal and governance barriers, particularly for decentralized sanitation approaches, pose significant obstacles. Additionally, there is a shortage of real-life demonstrations and effective communication of scientific results to the broader society. The public "yuk" factor, alongside fear and doubt surrounding new approaches, further complicates the situation. These challenges are exacerbated by the urgency of transformation processes, which are complex and time-consuming, and an economic system that currently favours non-circular and fossil-based systems. There is also a general misconception that ecological options are less economically viable, making it harder to engage companies in the circular economy. Moreover, without legislative changes, the collection and exploitation of feces remains impractical. Achieving investors and

decision-makers support, ensuring the safety of fertilizers, and making circular economy models more practical are critical issues, especially when dealing with cross-sectoral topics that intersect various legal frameworks (see Figure 37).

Figure 37: Overview identified challenges in the German pilot. WS2.

Addressing these challenges requires several key **needs** to be met. First, there must be clarification of legislative processes to replicate P2Green value chains effectively. There is also a need for application recommendations for agri-business operators, along with the identification of decision-makers and influencers who can support these initiatives. Investment and financing options are necessary, as is the identification of companies capable of transformative operations. Ecological considerations, such as the need for more information on current sanitation challenges and strategies to save and reuse water, are essential. Additionally, clear documentation of results is needed for effective dissemination. Particularly, in terms of what is demanded from local populations regarding risks associated with using fertilisers derived from human excreta. Collaboration between scientific communities and other societal forces is also crucial, and identifying local knowledge carriers is important for the creation of a centralized knowledge repository. Finally, generating a positive public narrative around these topics will aid in overcoming resistance.

The identified **benefits** of addressing these challenges include the creation of supportive networks, facilitating the exchange of experiences related to barriers and enablers, and the establishment of quality standards. There is also potential for job creation in rural areas, the development of solutions for clients, and the growing demand for organic fertilizers in regenerative agriculture.

Stakeholders can **contribute** to various aspects of governance and infrastructure by helping establish fertilizer quality standards, securing local funding, lobbying for legislative amendments, and communicating with investors about the reliability of investments. They can also contribute to education by organizing local events, forming networks for experience exchange, and developing replicable blueprints for fertilizer application. In the economic sphere, stakeholders can assist in capacity building, job creation, and the development of value chains and business cases. However, certain areas, such as fertilizer certification, quality assurance, and cost calculation for different target groups, remain outside the scope of what stakeholders can contribute.

Identified next steps:

The next steps identified by the stakeholders highlighted the need to explore the legislative framework, along with any national, federal, and municipal barriers that might hinder implementation processes in the German pilot. Additionally, cost estimates for implementation and comprehensive documentation of all processes are required. This should foster continuous and relevant communication with stakeholders. An in-person stakeholder engagement workshop was promoted to further foster collaboration with external stakeholders. It was communicated that stakeholders will be invited to visit the German test sites and observe developments firsthand.

WS2 - Spain

The Spanish workshop took place on the 24th of May 2023 (09.00 - 14.00 o'clock) and had 44 participants participating in person facilitated by the Spanish pilot partners (see Figure 38).

Figure 38: Stakeholder present in Spain. WS2

Most participants (84%) represented private enterprises. Further, 9% of participants are affiliated with research and academia. One participant was general public, and one represented an NGO.

Channels of communication:

- Relevant stakeholders were identified based on the stakeholder database and personal relations with relevant actors.

- The stakeholders considered to join the workshop were reached via personal Email and reminder emails (or phone calls).

Gender dimension:

The workshop included 44 participants, consisting of 16 female and 28 male participants. Representation of gender identities beyond the male and female categories was not explicitly reported in this workshop. Stakeholder groups, including public authorities, SMEs/businesses, NGOs, research/academia and the general public, were evenly represented. Going forward, workshop facilitators are encouraged to promote greater participation from a wider spectrum of individuals to ensure a broader representation of diverse gender identities. Further, a more gender-balanced participation is desired in the upcoming pilot activities.

Challenges, Needs, and Benefits:

The **challenges** identified focus on governance issues, building effective networks, and mediating with administrative bodies. Efficient management of reclaimed water is crucial, along with reducing associated costs and overcoming societal resistance to its use. Raising citizen awareness and promoting best practices are necessary, as it is improving access to digital tools and systems for both farmers and administrators. Key technical challenges include calculating precise irrigation and nutrient doses, implementing "water on demand" strategies, and utilizing real-time data processing with sensors. Scaling up treatment technologies and adapting infrastructures to make reclaimed water more accessible, while ensuring its quality, are also critical. Additionally, there is a need to study the nutrient content of reclaimed water, reduce its potential impact on soil, and estimate crop water requirements when using reclaimed water (see Figure 39).

Figure 39: Overview of identified challenges in the Spanish pilot. WS2

To address these challenges, the identified **needs** include encouraging the use of various water sources and addressing the current lack of training. Raising public awareness and promoting best practices are essential to the process, along with increasing knowledge and training around digital tools for the general public. Adaptation of European regulations and clear guidelines are necessary, as well as implementing a more sustainable agri-food system.

The **benefits** of addressing these needs include economic and energy savings and reduced water and fertilizer consumption. Digitization can enable precise nutrient and irrigation dosing based on crop needs, contributing to sustainable agriculture and the promotion of a circular economy (CE). These changes would promote a reduction in water and carbon footprints, less waste, and increased water availability.

Stakeholders can **contribute** to governance and infrastructure by lobbying relevant administrations, developing recommendations, and creating synergies through projects. They can propose and develop new projects, secure funding, and operational plans. In education, stakeholders can share success stories, promote P2Green results, and raise public awareness through campaigns, workshops, and conferences. They can also offer training on reclaimed water use, legislation, and risk management, and promote CE partnerships. Economically, stakeholders can help develop technology for reclaimed water, share data, and work on R&D projects to break the status quo. They can develop platforms and tools for better data utilization, provide expert consulting, and integrate IoT sensors and other digital tools into agriculture and industry.

Identified next steps:

In collaboration with participants, the focus was put on the visibility and dissemination of pilot activities. To advance the initiative, further workshops will be organized to showcase the pilot site and demonstrate the use of digital tools (e.g. smart aggregation tool). Additionally, collaboration with similar projects, such as NOVAFERT, GOVAQUA, and FERPLAY, was highlighted to foster knowledge exchange and strengthen the impact of these efforts.

WS 2 - Sweden

The Swedish stakeholder engagement workshop took place on the 13th of June 2023 (as part of the event “Demo Day”) at 17.00 o’clock and was facilitated by the Swedish pilot partners. At the workshop 25 actors participated in person. The exercises were slightly adjusted aiming to conduct all relevant insights based on the workshop development (see Figure 40).

Figure 40: Stakeholder present in Sweden. WS2

Over half (56%) of the participants represent private enterprises. Public authorities as well as research and academia are each represented by 12%. Another 20% are others.

Channels of communication:

- Stakeholders were invited in course of the Demo Day event and encouraged to join the workshop by the on-site project partners.

Gender dimension:

The workshop involved 25 participants, with 18 female and 7 male participants. Attendees are identified within a binary framework (m/f/d). Representation of gender identities beyond male and female categories was not specifically noted in this session. Stakeholder groups, such as public authorities, SMEs/businesses, NGOs, and research/academia, were well-represented. Moving forward, facilitators are encouraged to foster a more balanced gender representation, including non-binary and gender-diverse individuals, to ensure a more inclusive and diverse range of gender identities.

Challenges, Needs, and Benefits:

The identified **challenges** include a lack of incentives and subsidies, as well as vague or absent regulations and policies, which creates uncertainty. There is also an absence of clearly defined stakeholders and responsibilities regarding the collection, treatment, and distribution of resources like urine. Public acceptance and awareness remain low, compounded by a lack of research and development, pilot projects, and essential infrastructure (e.g., third pipes, and skilled plumbers). Furthermore, the high

cost of system implementation and components adds to these barriers (see Figure 41).

Figure 41: Overview of identified challenges in the Swedish pilot. WS2

The identified **needs** include ensuring food and fertilizer security, improving the efficiency of wastewater treatment plants (WWTP), and preventing the contamination of water with pharmaceutical and medical residues. These efforts also support climate change mitigation and help prevent eutrophication, which results in excessive algae growth.

The **benefits** of addressing these issues are substantial. They include the production of green-labelled products like fertilizers and beer, circular resource recovery, and the promotion of knowledge sharing on the circular economy (CE). Additionally, reducing greenhouse gas emissions from both fertilizer production and WWTP operations, ensuring compliance with treatment regulations, decreasing dependency on synthetic fertilizers, and enhancing water recovery and recycling are key advantages.

Stakeholders can **contribute** to governance and infrastructure by promoting food and fertilizer security, reducing system costs, and addressing the lack of infrastructure. They can also help improve WWTP efficiency. In the realm of education, stakeholders play a vital role in raising public awareness, transferring knowledge, and fostering research and development. From an ecological perspective, stakeholders can support the prevention of pharmaceutical and medical residue spread, reduce eutrophication, and contribute to climate change mitigation efforts.

Identified next steps:

Focus group interviews, originally planned for the workshop, were scheduled for August 2023 (M9) as part of Task 3.3. Following these interviews, the next steps for stakeholder engagement within the project will be discussed and outlined.

WS2 - Outcomes across pilots

Overall, 82 stakeholders were reached through the three stakeholder engagement workshops. All categories of stakeholders were represented. However, SMEs and businesses were represented by 67% percent as public authorities, which based on the identified issues are highly relevant actors, were represented by only 6% (see Table 24).

Stakeholders represented overall (clustered by category)	
Public authority	5 (6%)
SME/ business	55 (67%)
NGO	3 (4%)
Research/ academia	13 (16%)
General public	1 (1%)
Others (and not identified stakeholders)	5 (6%)

Table 24: Overview Stakeholders engaged across pilots. WS2

The identified issues are clustered to understand the overall topics brainstormed in the workshop's exercise of mapping challenges needs and benefits.

For the identified challenges, the overall categories are:

- **Regulatory and Governance:** this category comprises all challenges that refer to a set of policies, mechanisms, procedures, and organizations focused on the creation, execution, management, and enforcement of new rules or decisions. It encompasses the oversight and adjustment of regulations, regulators, and the guidelines that govern developments in the field of N&P recovery as well as bio-fertilization.
- **Society and Awareness:** this category comprises all challenges mentioning socio-economic factors as well as awareness and acceptance issues.
- **Technology and infrastructure:** the category includes challenges referring to technological and infrastructural deficits and developments in the pilot region. Investment in infrastructure, production, technological standards are also comprised by this category.

For the identified needs, the overall categories are:

- **Education:** the category includes educational needs such as improvement in knowledge, training, skills, and processes in the pilot region and among stakeholders operating in the area. Further, aspects of knowledge transfer and collaboration mechanisms are mentioned.
- **Governance and investment:** this category comprises needs concerning policies, collaboration mechanisms, procedures, and the implementation of new rules. Further, social as well as economic investments are included.
- **Ecological:** This category includes ecological components and developments. The category comprises aspects related to usage and emission as well as climate aspects.

For the identified benefits, the overall categories are:

- **Education:** similar as above.
- **Ecological:** similar as above.
- **Economical:** this category focuses on economic factors related to N&P recovery and bio fertilization. Aspect such as economic development, feasibility as well as demand and supply are comprised by this category.

In the following the most relevant issues listed among the stakeholders of all three workshops are presented based on their category (see Table 25).

Challenges	Needs	Benefits
Regulatory and Governance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Certification of fertilizers (GER) - Legislative amendments & governance framework (GER) - Lack of incentives and subsidies (SWE) - Lack of regulations & policies (vague and ambiguous) (SWE) - Mediation with administration (SPA) - Efficient management of reclaimed water (SPA) - Cost reduction (SPA) 	Education <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positive voice of the public on the topic (GER) - Awareness raising among citizens, promotion of best practice (SPA) - Increase knowledge and training tools (for the general public) (SPA) 	Education <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creation of a supportive network on the matter (GER) - Exchange of experiences (on barriers and enablers) (GER)
Society and Awareness <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How to find or create a broad societal acceptance? (GER) 	Governance and investment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clarification of legislative processes for the replication of P2Green value chain (GER) - Application recommendations for agri-business operations (GER) - Investment and financing (GER) - Food and fertilizer security (SWE) - Augmenting the efficiency in WWTP (SWE) - Adaptation of European regulations, clear guidelines (SPA) - Investment in infrastructures and sensors (SPA) 	Ecological <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Circular resource recovery (SWE) - Reduced GHG emission from fertilizer production & WWTP (SWE) - Enhancing water recovery and recycling (SWE) - Sustainable agriculture (SPA)

Technology and infrastructure	Ecological	Economical
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Making CE more practical (GER) - Investment and planning reliability for investors and decision makers (GER) - Create acceptance of investors and decision-makers (GER) - Knowledge on the potential of fertilization products (GER) - Safety of fertilizers (elimination of pollutants) (GER) - Lack of infrastructure, e.g. third pipe, plumbers (SWE) - Cost of the system (implementation, system components) (SWE) - Calculation of irrigation/nutrient dose (SPA) - Nutrient content of reclaimed water (SPA) - Adapt water quality for its use - Accessibility to digital tools and systems on all levels (farmers/ administrators) (SPA) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prevention of pharmaceutical, medical residues (SWE) - Climate change mitigation (SWE) - Prevention of eutrophication (excessive growth of algae) (SWE) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quality standards (GER) - Creation of jobs in rural areas (GER) - Reduce dependency on synthetic fertilizer (SWE) - Economic savings and savings in energy, water, and fertilizer (SPA) - Nutrient/ irrigation dosing adjusted to crop needs through digitization (SPA)

Table 25: Overview of identified challenges, needs, and benefits across pilots. WS2

The findings reveal significant challenges in regulatory and governmental aspects, such as a lack of regulatory guidelines and mediation with local public authorities, particularly concerning the certification of fertilizers derived from human excreta. The absence of clear regulations and certifications has been identified as an obstacle to efficient nutrient recovery management. This aligns with current research in circular economy, indicating that despite policy enhancements at national and international levels aiming at minimizing nutrient losses, the issue of fragmented and incomplete governance in nutrient recovery remains persistent (Aliahmad et al., 2023; McConville, 2017b). High implementation costs and the lack of innovative infrastructure were also identified as challenges. The need for social acceptance and awareness-raising efforts was highlighted across all pilots. Increasing societal awareness and knowledge is crucial to enhancing the acceptance and feasibility of new circular approaches. WS2 participants expressed concerns about the safety and potential residues in reclaimed water and fertilizers. As emphasized by Kirchmann et al. (2017) the potential risks associated with pollutants or pharmaceutical residues is a limiting factor in scaling up nutrient recovery. The development of knowledge and transfer networks was identified as a benefit of stakeholder participation in the project.

The challenges and needs identified among stakeholders in the three pilot regions underscore the importance of a systematic approach that addresses regulatory, societal, technological, and environmental factors (Larsen et al., 2021).

WS2 - Key outcomes

The outcomes of the workshops marked an initial activation of stakeholders, and a collaborative identification of existing challenges, needs, and benefits related to nitrogen and phosphorus (N&P) recovery, as well as P2Green's pilot activities. These

discussions highlighted the specific challenges faced by stakeholders in the different pilot regions, along with their individual needs and the potential benefits of engaging with the project. Overall, the workshops provided a clear mapping of the stakeholder landscape and identified the potential contributions each stakeholder can make to the success of the initiative.

4.5 Strategize: WS3 - Co-developed community-led strategies

The third round of stakeholder engagement workshops took place during the second COM, on the 17th and 19th of October 2023, in person in Malaga (M17). WS3 involved all pilot partners and interested project partners from other WPs. The workshop built on the outcomes of the two previous activities to further investigate which stakeholders were not successfully engaged and why. Further, the workshop was developed to answer the following questions:

- Who was not reached? / Who do we want to reach?
- Why were stakeholders not reached?
- How can we engage stakeholders who were not yet reached?

WS3 - Meetings and materials

Table 26 provides an overview of affiliated meetings. The regular WP4 meetings were used to regularly present and discuss the progress and are not specifically listed.

Workshop	Content	N Participants	Date	Facilitator
Strategy development workshop (WS3)				
Strategy development workshop: Germany	WS3 with pilot partners on stakeholder engagement strategies	13	17th of October 2023; 17.15 – 19.15	CBS & ICLEI
Strategy development workshop: Spain	WS3 with pilot partners on stakeholder engagement strategies	19	17th of October 2023; 17.15 – 19.15	CBS & ICLEI
Strategy development workshop: Sweden	WS3 with pilot partners on stakeholder engagement strategies	10	18th of October 2023; 15.15 – 17.15	CBS & ICLEI
Stakeholder strategies and engagement calendar				
Stakeholder engagement strategies: Germany, Spain & Sweden	Presentation of the outcomes from the strategy development workshop	13	11th of December 2023; 15.30 - 16.30	CBS
Training workshop on material developed				
Stakeholder engagement strategies and management: Germany	Presentation and training on developed strategies and stakeholder engagement calendar	10	5th of March 2024; 10.00 - 11.00	CBS

Stakeholder engagement strategies and management: Spain	Presentation and training on developed strategies and stakeholder engagement calendar	12	5 th of March 2024; 09.00 – 10.00	CBS
Stakeholder engagement strategies: Sweden	Presentation and training developed strategies and stakeholder engagement calendar	8	28 th of February 2024; 11.00 – 12.00	CBS
Dissemination material development workshops				
Dissemination material development: Germany, Spain & Sweden	Development of pilot-specific stakeholder engagement material	5	13 th of March 2024; 14.00 – 15.00	CBS & CIP
Bilateral talks on stakeholder engagement				
In-person talks on stakeholder engagement: Germany, Spain, Sweden	In-person talks on further support and usage of provided documents	All pilot partners	20 th to 23 rd of May 2024 (COM Gotland)	CBS

Table 26: Meetings WS3

WS3 - Method and tools

1st Activity: Challenges while engaging stakeholders

In the first activity, participants were asked to identify challenges faced during the stakeholder engagement process. Participants were encouraged to look at the list of participants from their previous workshop with external stakeholders (WS 2) and brainstorm on the topic: of why stakeholders might not have been involved (Figure 42).

1st Exercise: Stakeholder fact sheets and challenges engaging stakeholders

Overview of stakeholders

Guiding question: "Who was not reached and why?"

The goal: To identify challenges in the stakeholder engagement process.

What to do:

- Please to through the list and add missing relevant stakeholders
- Please reflect why stakeholders were not engaged yet
- Please write down which challenges you faced during the stakeholder engagement process
- Write down one challenge per post-it and place it on the template

Example:

Challenge 1: "Stakeholders are not responsive"
Challenge 2: "Stakeholders have busy schedules"

1. Challenges faced during stakeholder engagement process

Figure 42: 1st Exercise: Challenges in the stakeholder engagement process. WS3

2nd Activity: Actions to engage stakeholders

In the second exercise, partners were asked to reframe the previously listed challenges into “how might we” phrases. Through this exercise, the partners reframed challenges into concrete actions of how to overcome current difficulties in the stakeholder engagement process (Figure 43).

2nd Exercise: “How might we engage stakeholders?” Potential solutions

Guiding question: “How can we engage stakeholders who were not reached yet?”

The goal: Find possible solutions to overcome the challenges of engaging stakeholders/ How do we have to communicate and interact with these stakeholders

What to do:

- Go through the challenges listed in the previous exercise and reframe the listed challenges to “We might...” solutions
- Brainstorm on possible solutions to overcome the faced challenges
- The aim is to have a pool of potential solutions

Example:

Challenge: “Stakeholders are not responsive”

Potential solution: “We might align our activities with schedules of stakeholders and current events in the region to not overload stakeholders with events and information”

2. Possible solutions: “How might we...”

Figure 43: 2nd Exercise: How might we engage stakeholders. WS3

3rd Activity: Impact/ Effort matrix – Effective stakeholder engagement

In the final exercise of the workshop provided an Impact/Effort matrix and partners were asked to discuss and collectively place the developed solutions on the matrix (Figure 44).

3rd Exercise: Effective stakeholder engagement Identifying effective solutions

Guiding question: “How can we effectively engage stakeholders who have not been reached yet”

The goal: To identify effective solutions to engage missing stakeholders.

What to do:

- Please take the “We might...” solutions from the 2nd exercise and place them on the matrix
- Focus on the potential value of the solution and the effort to implement it
 - Focus on your resources/ and related effort
 - The context of your pilot region
 - Mechanisms within your organisations and others
- The value the solution would bring to your stakeholder engagement process

3. Ranking of “how might we solutions”

Figure 44: 3rd Exercise: Effective stakeholder engagement. WS3

WS3 - Reports and analysis

WS 3 - Germany

Internal challenges during the stakeholder engagement process:

The challenges identified during WS3 include several administrative and organizational obstacles. These range from navigating complex administrative systems and slow bureaucratic processes to a lack of knowledge about stakeholders' interests. Language barriers and time-consuming processes further complicate engagement efforts. Additionally, the absence of clearly defined responsibilities, coupled with fears of workload and accountability, hinders this process. Stakeholders are often unresponsive, uninterested, or sceptical of the project's value, and the lack of a single, identifiable contact person exacerbates these issues. Fast-paced implementation without purposeful planning is also flagged as a concern, while the use of administrative jargon poses communication challenges.

Other significant challenges include the limited availability of stakeholders, a lack of vision and flexibility, and hesitation among stakeholders to engage deeply with the project due to concerns about unforeseen complexities (referred to as the "Pandora's box" effect). Discontinuities in political and administrative support, as well as a lack of understanding of how different sectors operate, further isolate the project, which is often viewed as a niche topic. Stakeholders are reluctant to engage in non-profitable activities and lack the time for such efforts. There is also a need to identify key political figures and administrative practitioners to highlight the importance of the project and its actions.

In summary, challenges include issues related to responsibility, lack of continuity due to mismatches in timelines, and insufficient transparency. The absence of clear incentives, mismatches between needs and offers, and the need for defined and targeted communication strategies further complicate the engagement. The appropriate media channels, accessibility, entry points, and stakeholder expectations need to be clarified. Simplifying the project's message and incorporating elements of entertainment or lobbying are suggested as ways to increase interest and engagement.

Here it is important to highlight, that the changes in the pilot configuration (see section 3.3) did not affect the quality of the development of SE strategies for the German pilot. The organisational change in the pilot region did not affect the relevant external stakeholders and the engagement strategies.

Potential solutions to overcome the challenges (Impact/ Effort Matrix):

Several potential solutions have been proposed to overcome the challenges faced during stakeholder engagement, each rated based on the effort required and the potential impact (Figure 45).

Figure 45: Overview of impact/effort matrix in the German pilot. WS3

- **Low effort/low impact:** Solutions like utilizing ChatGPT for automation or emphasizing resilience in messaging require minimal effort but will likely have limited effects.
- **Low effort/medium impact:** Sending products to stakeholders' homes and ignoring minor rules by paying fines are low-effort strategies that could have some moderate impact. Additionally, connecting messages to binding political agendas can help build stakeholder relevance.
- **Low effort/high impact:** Shifting away from a "hippie, poopie" image, talking about tangible benefits such as money, jobs, and markets, and presenting the project as reversible can yield significant benefits without a large investment of resources. Inviting stakeholders to visit pilot sites or living labs, establishing a key reference project, and creating an internal ambassador for local authorities are also actions that require minimal effort but promise high returns.
- **Medium effort/low impact:** Learning from other sectors such as the climate debate and understanding the most effective measures versus ineffective approaches can enhance engagement with a reasonable amount of effort but might have limited immediate impact.
- **Medium effort/medium impact:** Attracting stakeholders through entertainment (e.g., keynote speakers), adapting project approaches to the specific needs of different territories, and focusing on farmer cooperatives using a bottom-up approach offer moderate impact for the effort invested. Engaging powerful NGOs to support the project can also foster stronger alliances.
- **Medium effort/high impact:** Engaging in discussions that create emotions (such as through art) and getting out of a purely normative approach could have a significant influence on stakeholder relationships and project visibility.

- **High effort/medium impact:** Listening to the voices of farmers and convincing influential figures on social media can help bring the project into broader public awareness, though this will require significant time and resources. Similarly, identifying the right contact person and exerting pressure on ministries are high-effort strategies that could yield solid results.
- **High effort/high impact:** The most effective but resource-intensive actions include lobbying for policy changes, building bridges of trust with stakeholders, changing administrative mechanisms, and increasing the lobbying budget. Establishing KPIs with authorities (e.g., expanding the number of living labs), defining specific homework for stakeholders, and creating meaningful connections by avoiding marginal contacts are high-effort strategies with the potential for substantial impact.

By categorizing these solutions according to their effort and potential impact, the pilot partners can focus on those actions that align best with its resources and goals.

WS3 - Spain

Internal challenges during the stakeholder engagement process:

The stakeholder engagement process faces several notable challenges. One of the primary issues is a lack of response and interest from stakeholders, who often prioritize other commitments or fail to see the immediate relevance or value of the P2Green project. The project is still in its early phases, which has contributed to limited visibility, particularly on social media (SoMe). This has made it difficult to attract attention and build momentum. Moreover, identifying and connecting with the right authorities, farmers, and relevant stakeholders has proven to be a challenging task, further complicating engagement efforts. Additionally, language barriers pose a significant obstacle in communication with diverse stakeholders across regions.

During a workshop, further communication challenges were identified. It was emphasized that the project needs a more defined and targeted core message to effectively convey its importance and benefits. Selecting the right media channels to reach different stakeholders, and adapting messages to be short, concise, and tailored to the audience, is essential. Simplifying and streamlining communication strategies is also critical to maintaining stakeholder interest. Moreover, the workshop highlighted the potential for using entertainment-based methods or lobbying efforts to increase engagement and make the project more appealing to broader audiences.

Potential solutions to overcome the challenges (Impact/ Effort Matrix):

To address the challenges faced in stakeholder engagement, several potential actions have been identified and rated based on their effort and impact (see Figure 46).

Figure 46: Overview impact/ effort matrix in the Spanish pilot. WS3

- **Low effort/low impact:** Increasing dissemination and communication activities at the pilot partner level, such as improving visibility on the websites of partners or disseminating targeted communication material, is a simple but limited strategy.
- **Medium effort/medium impact:** Exploring new sectors for the application of P2Green's solutions, such as gardening and landscaping, offers moderate effort with potential to broaden engagement and create new synergies. Improving and adapting the message to fit different audiences is another valuable approach that requires thoughtful consideration but can yield significant results.
- **Low effort/high impact:** Leveraging existing synergies with the project's network and related initiatives can enhance visibility and stakeholder interest with relatively low input. Translating P2Green's social media presence into Spanish can also expand its reach to a broader audience in a straightforward and impactful manner.
- **High effort/medium impact:** Directly reaching out to farmers by attending their meetings and briefly engaging with them could also prove highly effective, though it demands significant time and effort. Similarly, acknowledging stakeholder participation through incentives or small tokens of appreciation can enhance relationships and build long-term trust.
- **High effort/high impact:** The most impactful action involves reaching the right authorities, farmers, and stakeholders through targeted communication strategies. This requires a considerable investment of resources, but it can lead to deep, meaningful engagement with key players.

By prioritizing these actions based on their respective effort and impact, the P2Green pilot partners can streamline their stakeholder engagement process more effectively.

WS 3 - Sweden

The outcomes of the workshop highlighted several challenges faced during stakeholder engagement. Firstly, the project topic is inherently complex and hard to explain, making it difficult to engage stakeholders effectively. Many stakeholders are busy and struggle to allocate time and energy to the project. Additionally, there are no clear business models in place to demonstrate financial viability, and the lack of large-scale examples or projects means there are no successful precedents to learn from. This leads to a lack of interest among stakeholders. The challenge of upscaling the project adds another layer of complexity, with stakeholders being hesitant due to uncertainties about the outcomes and the absence of monetary incentives. There are no standardized system solutions, making it hard for stakeholders to visualize clear paths to implementation. Identifying the right stakeholders has also been difficult, and the project is sometimes disregarded because it's seen as not directly related to climate change—a topic that tends to attract more urgency.

Stakeholders often lack the time and energy to engage, and the activities offered may not align with their specific needs or expectations. There is also a lack of knowledge about, or even resistance to, concepts like urine diversion, which some stakeholders may find unfamiliar or unfavourable. Furthermore, many stakeholders tend to prioritize other issues, especially when budget constraints are a concern. Reaching stakeholders has been challenging due to low responsiveness or connecting with the wrong points of contact within organizations.

The workshop has also highlighted that there is no centralized process for engagement, and the project has been perceived as focusing only on phosphorus (P), which limits its appeal to a broader audience. Communication emerged as a key challenge. There is a lack of a targeted or core message, and uncertainty about which media or communication channels would be most effective. The messaging needs to be adapted—potentially shortened and simplified to suit the audience better. It was also suggested to broaden the range of activities to engage stakeholders more effectively, such as through hackathons or similar interactive formats. Providing acknowledgment or incentives for stakeholder participation would also help to keep them engaged.

In summary, the pilot partners must better adjust to stakeholders' needs, and the communication should be streamlined and simplified to increase clarity and engagement. The workshop also recommended using more creative outreach strategies, such as incorporating entertainment or lobbying, to better communicate the project's value and encourage broader participation.

Potential solutions to overcome the challenges (Impact/ Effort Matrix)

Potential solutions to overcome the challenges are illustrated below (see Figure 47).

Figure 47: Overview impact/ effort matrix in the Swedish pilot. WS3

- **Low effort/low impact:** Conducting a simple survey to collect feedback on activities of interest from stakeholders and providing short policy briefs on how new directives may affect them are straightforward strategies with limited impact.
- **Low effort/high impact:** Sharing best practices for engaging stakeholders and distributing low-cost promotional materials, like T-shirts and pins, can significantly enhance visibility and encourage participation with minimal effort.
- **Medium effort/medium impact:** Creating infographics and videos in local languages, along with linking the project to broader issues like climate change, requires moderate effort but can increase relevance and understanding across diverse audiences. Regular press releases in local media also boosts visibility.
- **Medium effort/high impact:** Booking stakeholders for events well in advance and following up one-on-one to address specific concerns helps build stronger relationships and ensures participation, though it demands more planning and coordination.
- **High effort/high impact:** Establishing meaningful two-way dialogues with stakeholders and investing in direct communication, like attending stakeholder events and making cold calls, requires substantial resources but leads to deep, lasting engagement.

WS3 - Outcomes

- List of challenges faced during the stakeholder engagement process
- List of potential actions to overcome the challenges
- Clustering of actions according to effort and impact
- Development of Stakeholder engagement plan
- Development of Stakeholder engagement calendar

5. Stakeholder engagement strategies

In the following section, the summary of the co-created and community-led engagement strategies is presented. The strategies are based on the outcomes of the reported workshops, and various internal co-creation meetings between the pilot partners, and collaborations between WP6 and WP4. Additionally, the insights of the conducted market assessments for three pilot regions provided a deeper understanding of the local contexts. The strategies are crafted to ensure a continued and effective engagement of relevant stakeholders in P2Green's pilot regions.

The strategies are targeted to create regional stakeholder networks, which is required to operationalise P2Green's innovative systems solutions so that P2Green creates the required wider impact across its pilot regions. Through the strong co-creation approach, and the incorporation of stakeholders' perspectives, the engagement strategies are built based on the needs of internal project partners and external stakeholders. The guidelines can enable the crafting and adapting of the 'core message' of each pilot region, to drive the interests of various tentative public, private, and business partners. The full SE plan for each pilot region can be found in appendix D; D.2 & D.4. The engagement strategies are accompanied by a calendar developed for each pilot region (see appendix D.1; D.3 & D.5). This document provides support in the planning effort for identified SE activities. The stakeholder engagement plans provide a comprehensive overview of co-created strategies to effectively engage stakeholders (Strategize & Execute – WS3), based on an assessment of identified local, national, and international stakeholders (Map & Gain overview – WS1), as well as current challenges and needs in the field (Gain overview & Activate – WS2). The co-created strategies are designed based on the local context and will be continuously revised and further adjusted throughout the project's duration. The evaluation survey provided deep feedback on the applied SE methodology and usability of the strategies. Continuous evaluation and feedback will support the implementation and further execution.

Below, the co-created SE strategies are presented (see Figure 48, Figure 49 and Figure 50). The first stage of the SE strategies focuses on immediate actions, which can be implemented with rather low effort. Additionally, it provides an overview of activities that can be combined with other solutions. The second stage of the SE strategies, highlights activities that can be carried out over time. These activities need to be implemented considering the planning effort. The strategies should be considered in the local context.

After presenting the pilot specific co-created stakeholder engagement strategies, a combined overview of the suggested strategies (see Table 27) as well as activities, across pilots (see Table 28) is provided.

5.1 Spain

The SE strategies for the Spanish pilot mostly focus on enhancing communication efforts. Especially, the tone of core messages communication is highlighted. It is of high importance to create targeted messages to different stakeholder groups, combining the analysis of the local stakeholder landscape and already engaged stakeholders. To ensure continuous engagement, internal resources should be dedicated. For example, the identification of the right channel, a dedicated community manager as well as adjusted messages should be defined. This process will be continuously executed in collaboration between the pilot partners, WP4 and WP6.

Figure 48: Stakeholder engagement strategies for the Spanish pilot

5.2 Germany

For the German pilot, communication efforts are highlighted. Targeted and well-communicated core messages could build meaningful connections with diverse groups of stakeholders. Especially, collaboration with local authorities is important to be involved in administrative mechanisms and showcase the high relevance of the pilot's activities. The strategies were developed throughout the project and consider the changes in the German pilot region (see in section 3.3).

Figure 49: Stakeholder engagement strategies for the German pilot

5.3 Sweden

Besides communication efforts and community building, the SE strategies for the Swedish pilot focus on local education and the distribution of knowledge. Pro-active and knowledge-led engagement would increase the public awareness and interest in the pilot activities in a wider scope.

Stakeholder engagement Strategies Swedish pilot

Can be done immediately

Low effort – high impact

Foster a sense of community among stakeholders.

- ✓ Amplify the project brand visibility by creating marketing material (e.g. t-shirts, pins etc.)
- Ensure the marketing materials reflect the project brand identity
- Explore eco-friendly materials In line with the commitment to sustainability

Communication

Share Best Practices.

- ✓ Disseminate best practices for stakeholder engagement through workshops, webinars, or a dedicated online portal, to share lessons learned and innovative ideas
- ✓ Implement feedback mechanisms to encourage stakeholders to share their experiences and insights

Educational Initiatives.

- ✓ Forge partnerships with educational stakeholders to integrate the project values and goals into curricular activities

Administrative

Can be combined with other solutions

Low effort – low impact

Conducting a survey to gauge stakeholder interests.

- ✓ Develop a comprehensive survey to understand the preferences and expectations of our stakeholders.
- ✓ Analyze survey results to identify key areas of interest and areas for improvement

Communication

Keep local stakeholders informed about the impact of regulatory changes.

- ✓ Timely Communication: provide stakeholders with a policy brief outlining the effects of the new directive.
- ✓ Organize Q&A sessions to address any queries or concerns arising from the new directive

Administrative

Evaluate pain and gain before implementing

Medium/ high effort – medium impact

Create more targeted messages.

- ✓ Create core message and communication material (Infographics, Info Videos)
- ✓ Align your initiatives with broader topics such as climate change to enhance relevance and impact
- ✓ Regularly issue press releases to keep stakeholders and the public informed about our initiatives, achievements, and milestones

Communication

Be proactive!

- ✓ Establish targeted contacts with media outlets, including Radio P1 and P4, Land, and ATL, to ensure effective coverage and dissemination
- ✓ Conduct personalized follow-up meetings to address individual stakeholder concerns and maintain strong relationships
- ✓ Plan and schedule engagements with stakeholders three months in advance to ensure effective coordination and participation

Evaluate pain and gain before implementing

Medium/ high effort – medium impact

Showcase a Way Out of Bureaucracy.

- ✓ Illustrate the commitment to navigating and streamlining bureaucratic processes for the benefit of the pilot stakeholders

Administrative

Technical Innovation (Urinals/Urine Division):

- ✓ Embrace and communicate advancements in urinal technology and urine division practices, highlighting our commitment to technical innovation and sustainability

Resources

To be achieved over time

High effort – high impact

Increase dissemination and communication activities at pilot level

- ✓ Tailor innovative events, such as a Hackathon, to align with stakeholder interests and industry trends
- ✓ Prioritize direct communication channels such as cold-calls over emails to ensure a more personal and immediate connection
- ✓ Establish a dedicated process for facilitating two-way dialogues with stakeholders within 30 minutes of their outreach

Communication

Explore Funds opportunities

- ✓ Establish a dedicated team or individual responsible for identifying and securing funds to support engagement initiatives
- ✓ Explore partnerships, sponsorships, and grant opportunities to ensure sustainable funding for impactful engagement programs

Resources

To be achieved over time

High effort – high impact

Show Up at Events of Stakeholders:

- ✓ Emphasize the importance of personal presence – both physically and virtually – in all engagement activities.
- ✓ Encourage pilot team members to actively participate in industry events, conferences, and stakeholder meetings to build strong, face-to-face connections

Administrative

Figure 50: Stakeholder engagement strategies for the Swedish pilot

5.4 Summary Co-developed stakeholder engagement strategies for Spain, Germany, and Sweden

In the following an overview of stakeholder engagement strategies across all pilot regions is provided (Table 27).

Strategy	Output	Target Audience	Frequency	Specific Pilot
Create targeted messages	Targeted, effective messaging. Focus on economic impacts, job creation, market relevance	Farmers, regional authorities, economic actors	Ongoing	Germany, Sweden
Use effective channels	Utilize online and offline channels, including local platforms			Spain, Sweden
Adjust for local context	Acknowledge diversity within farming communities and territories			Germany, Sweden
Build personal and meaningful relationships	Appoint dedicated communication ambassadors, tangible outcomes	Policymakers, farmers' representatives, NGOs	Ongoing	Germany, Sweden
Share tangible outcomes	Project progress reports, invitations to test sites			Germany, Sweden
Create synergies	Collaborate with similar projects, co-create events			Experts, farmers, stakeholders
Be proactive	Research and participate in stakeholder activities, both online and offline	Stakeholders from agriculture, energy, sustainability projects	Ongoing	Spain, Sweden
Use stakeholder-specific language	Translate outreach activities into local languages, adjust tone and message	Local farmers, NGOs, policymakers	Ongoing	Spain, Sweden

Incentivize stakeholders	Provide small rewards (e.g., fruit samples) to spark interest	Local farmers, experts, general public	Event-based	Spain, Sweden
Get away from stereotypes	Professional image for pilot, steer away from stereotypical associations	General public, experts, academics, influencers	Ongoing	Germany, Sweden
Create emotions	Use storytelling, entertainment, and emotional content for engagement	General public, NGOs, influencers, social media	Event-based	All (Spain, Germany, Sweden)
Collaborate with agricultural and energy influencers	Form strategic partnerships with farmers, cooperatives, influencers	Farmers, cooperatives, NGOs, influencers	Ongoing	Germany, Sweden
Engage policymakers	Strengthen lobbying efforts, push for budget allocations, and policy changes	Policymakers, local authorities, ministry representatives	Regular meetings	Germany, Sweden
Focus on sustainability goals	Tie project efforts to Sweden's national sustainability and climate goals	Policymakers, energy stakeholders, farmers	Ongoing	Sweden

Table 27: Summary Co-developed stakeholder engagement strategies for Spain, Germany, and Sweden

5.5 Summary target activities within co-developed stakeholder engagement and strategies for Spain, Germany, and Sweden

In the following section, a summary of all SE activities across the three pilot regions is provided. To develop and facilitate effective SE activities a strategic approach is of importance. To engage stakeholders effectively, it must be ensured that everyone involved in the process understands and shares common goals, values, and expected contributions. This preparation will help make activities as productive as possible. Additionally, it is important to communicate shared expectations by either collecting feedback from prior goal-setting sessions or inviting stakeholders to express their expectations for the engagement (Table 28).

Activity	Description	Target Audience	Frequency	Specific Pilot
Regular meetings with stakeholders/ Town Hall meetings	Create a core group of stakeholders to engage them with pilot progress updates	Policymakers, experts, NGOs, farmers	Every 6 months	Germany, Sweden
External events participation	Scan and participate in relevant events to promote P2Green and engage stakeholders	Experts, academics, partner projects, NGOs, policymakers, farmers	On-demand	Spain, Germany, Sweden
Info days, workshops, and field visits	Organize visits and workshops to showcase test sites and pilot progress	Experts, academics, partner projects, NGOs, policymakers, farmers	Every 12 months	All (Spain, Germany, Sweden)
Share dissemination and	Disseminate project outcomes via local	General public, experts,	Every 6 months	All (Spain, Germany, Sweden)

information material	newspapers, venues, press releases	academics, policymakers, NGOs, farmers		
Door-to-Door & 1:1 communication	Informal communication and dissemination material to spread project awareness	General public, experts, academics, partner projects, policymakers	Continuously	Spain, Sweden
Social media outreach & blog entries	Create project updates, repost content, and collaborate with influencers	General public, experts, academics, partner projects, policymakers	SoMe (twice a month), Blog (every 3 months)	All (Spain, Germany, Sweden)
Emails/ newsletters/ press releases	Continuous communication with stakeholders on pilot outcomes and technology updates	General public, experts, academics, partner projects, policymakers	Every 3 months	All (Spain, Germany, Sweden)

Table 28: Summary target activities within co-developed stakeholder engagement and strategies for Spain, Germany and Sweden

6. Feedback survey

Evaluation methodology

This section presents the outcomes of a consortium internal feedback survey on the stakeholder engagement methodology carried out. The survey consisted of 16 questions and was designed to be completed within approximately 15 minutes. The survey was distributed internally within the P2Green partners using the Qualtrics platform. Data were provided anonymously, and a consent form was sent to ensure participants' privacy. Respondents were asked to rate statements on a Likert scale ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree." For questions regarding the ranking of stakeholders engaged the most and those most relevant for further engagement, a ranking scale from 0 to 5 was used, where 0 represented "least relevant" and 5 indicated "most relevant." The survey was designed to receive feedback on:

- The overall SE process
- Stakeholders engaged
- Tools used

Overall feedback on SE process

Out of 35 collected responses, 18 were eligible for analysis. Most survey participants (62%) were involved as participants in the SE process, while the remaining 38% were organizers of SE activities. Additionally, 56% of participants were from the SME/business field, 28% from research and academia, 11% from NGOs, and 5% from public authorities (see appendix E).

A majority (56%) of respondents found the SE process to be satisfactory, indicating a general level of contentment among the stakeholders involved. Furthermore, a significant portion (17%) expressed that the process was very satisfactory, which reflects positively on the engagement efforts. However, 22% rated the SE as either unsatisfactory or poor, highlighting potential areas that need to be addressed. This

finding suggests the need for further investigation into the reasons behind these ratings to identify specific areas for enhancement (see Figure 51).

Figure 51: Stakeholder engagement process. Evaluation survey

Overall, most respondents (61.1%) indicated a positive perception of the clarity of the SE process objectives, with 55.6% somewhat agreeing and 5.6% strongly agreeing. 16.7% of respondents who chose "neither agree nor disagree" suggest that a small group either felt indifferent or did not have enough information to form a clear opinion. There was the presence of dissenting views, as 22.2% expressed disagreement with the clarity of the objectives, highlighting the importance of continuous improvement in communication strategies. It should be noted that a significant 38.9% of respondents had issues preparing materials and resources for the SE activities, highlighting notable challenges in the preparation process. Conversely, 44.4% expressed some level of agreement, suggesting that while some found the process manageable, a substantial number did not have enough information to form a clear opinion on the SE process objectives.

Most participants (61.1%) felt there was adequate support for executing the SE activities, reflecting a generally positive perception of the support provided. However, 22.2% pointed to concerns about the sufficiency of this support. A substantial majority of respondents (66.7%) felt there were sufficient internal meetings with WP4 partners, indicating a positive sentiment regarding communication and collaboration within WP4. Conversely, 11.1% of participants disagreed, suggesting that some may have felt the need for more frequent or targeted meetings. This feedback highlights the importance of evaluating meeting structures to enhance SE further. Additionally, this highlights the importance of continuous communication among partners.

Feedback on stakeholders engaged

The survey results indicate strong engagement with research/academia (4.17), suggesting effective collaboration and interest in P2Green's activities. In contrast, engagement levels are moderate for SMEs/businesses (2.92) and public authorities (2.36), while the general public (2.08) and NGOs (1.31) show the least engagement, highlighting areas for improvement. To enhance overall stakeholder involvement,

further targeted strategies should be implemented, particularly to engage NGOs and the general public effectively (see Figure 52).

Figure 52: Stakeholders engaged. Evaluation survey

The survey results highlight that public authorities (4.43) are considered the most relevant stakeholders for further engagement, indicating their crucial role in the SE process. Research/academia (3.50) and the general public (3.75) also show significant relevance, suggesting that continued collaboration and outreach efforts are beneficial. In contrast, while SMEs/businesses (3.07) and NGOs (2.45) are deemed less relevant for immediate engagement, there remains an opportunity to strengthen connections with these groups to enhance the overall impact of the SE process.

Feedback on tools used

The survey responses indicate that 50% of participants somewhat agreed that WP4 provided sufficient methods to address issues during the SE process, showing a generally positive reception of the support offered. However, 16.7% disagreed or strongly disagreed, suggesting that some participants felt that the methods were insufficient. Additionally, 33.3% remained neutral, indicating that a portion of the respondents may require further clarification or improvements to better align the method with stakeholder expectations (see Figure 53).

Figure 53: Stakeholder management. Evaluation survey

Perceptions of the SE process's adaptability to local needs were divided. While 27.8% somewhat agreed, and 11.1% strongly agreed that it was adaptable, 27.8% disagreed or strongly disagreed, revealing significant challenges in this area. A large portion

(44.4%) neither agreed nor disagreed, pointing to mixed experiences regarding the flexibility of the process and suggesting potential areas for improvement in further tailoring the SE process to local contexts.

Keeping stakeholders informed and engaged was generally seen as manageable, with 22.2% strongly agreeing and 38.9% somewhat agreeing. However, 27.8% disagreed or strongly disagreed, indicating some difficulties in maintaining engagement. The neutral responses (33.3%) suggest that experiences in this area varied, highlighting the need for more consistent engagement strategies to ensure stakeholders remain actively involved throughout the process. These neutral responses may also reflect the fluctuating nature of stakeholder involvement, indicating that the engagement process can be easier at times and more challenging at others.

The results highlight challenges in coordinating external stakeholders, with only 27.8% somewhat or strongly agreeing that coordination was straightforward. Another 27.8% disagreed or strongly disagreed, while 44.4% neither agreed nor disagreed, suggesting uncertainty or a mix of experiences. This feedback underscores the need for improved coordination strategies to ensure more effective collaboration with external stakeholders in future projects.

The survey participants also perceive obtaining timely and meaningful feedback from external stakeholders as a challenge. While 33.3% somewhat or strongly agreed that it was easy, 27.8% disagreed, and 38.9% remained neutral. This suggests that there are gaps in communication and feedback mechanisms, indicating a need for enhanced strategies to facilitate more effective and timely feedback collection from external stakeholders.

Overcoming resistance to new ideas or approaches posed a moderate challenge during the SE process. While 42.1% of respondents disagreed or strongly disagreed that this was a significant issue, 36.8% somewhat or strongly agreed, indicating that for a notable portion of participants, resistance was indeed a barrier. The neutral responses (21.1%) suggest that experiences with resistance may have been context dependent.

Convincing stakeholders to commit to the project proved to be a challenge. A significant portion of respondents (38.9%) either strongly disagreed or disagreed, indicating difficulties in gaining stakeholder commitment. Neutral responses (44.4%) suggest that many were undecided or faced mixed results, while only 16.7% found it somewhat or strongly easy to secure commitment, highlighting a potential area for improvement in engagement strategies.

Showcasing the viability of the project's values to stakeholders was a challenge for many respondents. A notable 44.4% either strongly disagreed or disagreed that it was easy, indicating difficulty in demonstrating the project's relevance or benefits. Additionally, 27.8% of respondents remained neutral, suggesting uncertainty, while only 27.8% somewhat or strongly agreed that this task was manageable. This highlights a potential need for clearer communication, or a more effective demonstration of the project's core values to stakeholders.

The "stakeholder mapping tool" (WS1) proved to be useful for most respondents, with 61.1% somewhat or strongly agreeing that it helped identify and map stakeholders effectively. A smaller portion, 22.2%, remained neutral, while only 16.7% disagreed or

strongly disagreed. This indicates overall satisfaction with the tool, though there is room for refinement to better support all users in the mapping process. The use of the stakeholder database in subsequent activities received mixed responses. While 33.3% of participants somewhat or strongly agreed that it was utilized, 33.3% neither agreed nor disagreed, suggesting uncertainty or limited use. A notable 33.3% disagreed or strongly disagreed, indicating that the stakeholder list may not have been fully integrated into further activities for a significant portion of respondents. This highlights an area for improvement in ensuring the stakeholder database's utility throughout the project.

The tool, “mapping challenges and needs of stakeholders” (used during WS2, the external stakeholder workshop in all three pilots), was generally considered helpful for identifying stakeholder challenges and needs, with 58.8% of respondents somewhat or strongly agreeing with its effectiveness. However, 23.5% neither agreed nor disagreed, which might suggest that its utility was unclear to some participants. A smaller group (17.6%) disagreed or strongly disagreed, indicating that the tool may need refinement to better address all users' needs in identifying stakeholder challenges. 13.2. The challenges and needs identified during the process were utilized in subsequent activities, with 53.8% of respondents indicating some level of agreement (somewhat or strongly agree) with this statement. However, a notable portion (46.2%) either disagreed, strongly disagreed, or remained neutral, suggesting that the integration of these insights into future actions may not have been fully effective or clear to all participants.

The tool used to identify the “potential contributions of stakeholders to pilot activities” (WS 2) was perceived positively, with 58.8% of respondents indicating some level of agreement (somewhat or strongly agree). However, a notable 23.5% of participants either disagreed or strongly disagreed, while 17.6% remained neutral. This suggests that while many found the tool helpful, there is still room for improvement in its usability or the clarity of its purpose for all users. Addressing these concerns may enhance stakeholder engagement and contribution to future projects.

The tool designed for “brainstorming concrete actions to overcome challenges” (WS3) in the SE process received a generally positive response. A total of 52.9% of respondents expressed some level of agreement (somewhat or strongly agree), indicating that many found it effective for collecting actionable ideas. However, 29.4% of participants disagreed or strongly disagreed, suggesting some challenges in usability or effectiveness. Additionally, 17.6% remained neutral. The feedback on the use of strategies co-developed during the SE process indicates a mixed response. While 46.2% of respondents (somewhat agree or strongly agree) utilized these strategies in further activities, 15.4% (disagree or strongly disagree) did not find them beneficial. Additionally, 38.5% of participants expressed neutrality, suggesting uncertainty about the effectiveness of the strategies. This indicates an opportunity for improvement, possibly through additional training or resources to enhance the application of these strategies in future activities.

Lessons for next steps

In conclusion, the analysis of the survey results reveals a mixed but generally positive perception of the SE process among the respondents. While a majority (56%) expressed satisfaction with the process, a notable 22% reported unsatisfactory

experiences, indicating areas for improvement, particularly in communication and support strategies. The findings emphasize the importance of continued engagement with key stakeholders, especially public authorities. Furthermore, the feedback suggests a need for enhancing the adaptability of the SE process to local needs and improving tools for stakeholder mapping and challenge identification to foster more effective collaboration in future initiatives.

The survey analysis from the P2Green pilot regions underscores the critical need for enhanced communication strategies and adaptability to local contexts. Clear messaging tailored to diverse stakeholder groups, especially public authorities, and local communities, is essential to foster understanding and engagement. Organizing targeted workshops and informational sessions will help clarify project objectives and benefits while conducting local needs assessments can ensure the SE process is responsive to the unique challenges of each region.

Additionally, improving stakeholder coordination and developing robust feedback mechanisms are vital for effective collaboration. Establishing structured frameworks for coordination, along with designated liaisons, will facilitate communication and inclusivity. Implementing streamlined processes for feedback collection will empower stakeholders and demonstrate that their input is valued. Finally, fostering stakeholder commitment through showcasing tangible benefits and addressing concerns will be crucial for ensuring active participation and successful outcomes in the SE process.

In the next steps of T4.2, these challenges will be addressed in a structured and targeted way. Continuous conversation with pilot partners will be fostered to ensure further engagement of local stakeholders and assist partners in developing the regional stakeholder network, which is required to operationalise P2Green's innovative systems solutions so that P2Green continuously creates the required wider impact across its pilot regions.

7. Conclusion and Outlook

Effective stakeholder engagement is essential to the success of the P2Green project, as it is incorporated across various work packages and tasks in different formats. Maintaining efficient engagement strategies requires close collaboration among all work packages.

The SE process will continuously be carried out through the P2Green project. Major learnings come from the evaluation survey and will be incorporated into the next SE activities. Both the engagement strategies as well as the engagement plan and calendar will be continuously updated. Deliverable 4.4 will provide guidelines to support local and regional governments implementing a circular nutrient flow, therefore creating a tangible outcome that can be shared to involve public authorities identified as relevant stakeholders that need further engagement. Additionally, the collaboration with WP6 will further craft specific communication material for targeted external and internal stakeholders. Finally, an evaluation survey at the end of the P2Green project will provide additional learnings and insights from project partners. This will ensure meaningful reflections on the method applied as well as a broader impact of P2Green.

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9. Appendix:

Appendix A: Agenda WS1

5 min	People presentation
10 min	Project presentation: focus on pilot region and tested technologies and highlighting the benefits for stakeholders to be involved in the project
20 min	Brainstorming in small groups on key issues relating to the needs, challenges (including social) and potential benefits from participating in the project and more broadly in nutrient recovery (remember to take pictures when done)
10 min	Present and discuss/ clarify identified needs and challenges
5 min	break
20 min	Ranking the identified needs, challenges and potential benefits from participating in the project and more broadly in nutrient recovery, in the relevant ranking table (remember to take pictures when done)
10 min	Discuss/ Clarify and select the most relevant ones
5 min	break
20 min	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In/out activity: for participants to indicate which and how they can contribute to the most relevant challenges and needs (remember to take pictures when done) • Mapping stakeholder cooperation: Are you working with local authorities; with whom and in what capacity regarding nutrient recovery or any other topic (i.e. spatial and urban planning, wastewater management or agricultural policy)? Are there any co-ordination mechanisms in place for this co-operation?
15 min	<p>Discuss/align activities and expectations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The final section of the workshop should clarify the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How much each stakeholder would like to engage in the project activities. Some stakeholders may simply want updates from the project as to how it is progressing, whereas others may want to take part in future workshops to assist in the development of the use cases etc. Finding this out is important for the future workshops. • Possible option of involvement according to the survey: stakeholder should shortly summarize their expected involvement. • Collection (on post-its): Are some stakeholders missing in the workshop that should be included in the upcoming workshops/project progress? • Collection (on post-its): Potential challenges, what do we need to consider if we want to implement our solution/use cases, what could be potential pitfalls?
10 min	Lay out the plan for next steps based on in/out activity
5 min	break
30-40 min	Focus group interviews (T3.3)
5 min	Wrap up

Appendix A.1: Pictures WS 1

Appendix B: Agenda WS 2

5 min	People presentation
10 min	Project presentation: focus on pilot region and tested technologies and highlighting the benefits for stakeholders to be involved in the project
20 min	Brainstorming in small groups on key issues relating to the needs, challenges (including social) and potential benefits from participating in the project and more broadly in nutrient recovery (remember to take pictures when done)
10 min	Present and discuss/ clarify identified needs and challenges
5 min	break
20 min	Ranking the identified needs, challenges, and potential benefits from participating in the project and more broadly in nutrient recovery, in the relevant ranking table (remember to take pictures when done)
10 min	Discuss/ Clarify and select the most relevant ones
5 min	break
20 min	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In/out activity: for participants to indicate which and how they can contribute to the most relevant challenges and needs (remember to take pictures when done) • Mapping stakeholder cooperation: Are you working with local authorities; with whom and in what capacity regarding nutrient recovery or any other topic (i.e., spatial, and urban planning, wastewater management or agricultural policy)? Are there any co-ordination mechanisms in place for this co-operation?
15 min	<p>Discuss/align activities and expectations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The final section of the workshop should clarify the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ How much each stakeholder would like to engage in the project activities. Some stakeholders may simply want updates from the project as to how it is progressing, whereas others may want to take part in future workshops to assist in the development of the use cases etc. Finding this out is important for the future workshops. ○ Possible option of involvement according to the survey: stakeholder should shortly summarize their expected involvement. ○ Collection (on post Its): Are some stakeholders missing in the workshop that should be included in the upcoming workshops/project progress? ○ Collection (on post Its): Potential challenges, what do we need to consider if we want to implement our solution/use cases, what could be potential pitfalls?
10 min	Lay out the plan for next steps based on in/out activity
5 min	break
30-40 min	Focus group interviews (T3.3)
5 min	Wrap up

Appendix B.1: Reporting template WS2

General information	
Pilot region:	
Date and host of Workshop:	
Number of attendees:	
Which stakeholder groups were represented?	<p>For each stakeholder group, please specify:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • potential contribution • current and desired level of engagement

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The stakeholder's expectations from the pilot/participation in the project Channel(s) of communication used to reach them
Which stakeholders were not reached and why?	
Identified needs and challenges	
Identified local needs:	<i>(Please list all of them)</i>
Identified local challenges:	<i>(Please list all of them)</i>
Identified local benefits:	<i>(Please list all of them)</i>
Which were the prioritised needs?	<i>(Please list only the needs ranked as most relevant)</i>
Which were the prioritised challenges?	<i>(Please list only the challenges ranked as most relevant)</i>
Which were the prioritised benefits?	<i>(Please list only the benefits ranked as most relevant)</i>
Stakeholder relationships and existing processes	

Interest of stakeholders (to participate in the workshop and P2Green overall):	
Identified relations and coordination mechanisms between stakeholders:	
Ideas to support the development and coordination process between stakeholder, if any were discussed/mentioned during the meeting:	
Next steps	
What are the next steps? (Please indicate activities/aspects to engage the different stakeholder groups based on their availability and their expertise)	

Appendix B.2: Reporting template WS2

Appendix C: Agenda WS3

5 min	Introduction
10 min	Presentation of stakeholders who were not reached (based on the two previous workshops)
15 min	Why were stakeholders not reached? Exercise: Goals and challenges mapping
5 min	Present and discuss/ clarify identified goals and challenges
5 min	break
15 min	How can we engage stakeholders who were not reached yet? Exercise: How might we overcome the challenges in engaging specific stakeholders <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ How do we have to communicate with these stakeholders
5min	Present and discuss/ clarify HMW
15 min	How can we engage stakeholders who were not reached yet? Exercise: Matrix/ ranking of effectiveness of the “how might we...” solutions
5 min	Present and discuss/ clarify matrix
5 min	break
20 min	Activity ICLEI
10 min	Discuss/align activities and expectations + next steps and questions
5 min	Wrap up

Appendix C.1: Pictures WS3

Appendix D: Stakeholder engagement plan Germany

1 Stakeholder mapping.

Through the previous project activities, we defined a list of relevant stakeholders for your region also indicating the field of operation and relevance. In the kick-off meeting in January 2023, you mapped 72 stakeholders and indicated the high relevance of 25 actors.

Keep in mind about your stakeholders:

- What do they already know about the project?
- What do they need to know?
- Their power to affect or influence the project.
- Their interest and sentiment toward the project.

2 Stakeholder insights.

From your first stakeholder engagement workshop, we gained some insights into the challenges and needs of your local stakeholders. We also collected the potential benefits your stakeholders see in our project.

Challenges your stakeholders face:

- Lack of clear and safe vision
- Certification of fertilizers
- Lack of acceptance by farmers and lack of knowledge about fertilization potential
- Legislative barriers to decentralize fertilization approaches
- Too few real-life demonstrations or living labs
- Overcome the common understanding that ecological solutions cannot be the most economical ones
- The current system privileges non-circular and fossil systems
- Making circular economy more practical
- Frustration: "Collection of fees can be done but makes no sense as long as legislation is prohibitive"
- Cross-sectoral topic touching various judicial regimes
- Create acceptance of investors and decision-makers
- Safety of fertilizers (elimination of pollutants)

Needs of stakeholders:

- Clarification of the legislative process for the replication of P2GreenN value chains
- Application recommendations for agri-business operators
- Identification of decision-makers and multipliers
- Identifying companies with transformative potential and operations
- Need for investment and financing options
- More information about the ecological challenges based on the current sanitation system
- Save and reuse water
- Joint forces and societal change
- Cooperation of the scientific community with other actors
- Positive voice of the public on the topic

Benefits for stakeholders:

- Creation of a supportive network on the matter
- Experience exchange
- Define quality standards
- Creation of jobs in rural areas
- Increase demand for organic fertilizers in regenerative agriculture

3 Engagement strategies.

General & Visibility:

Build personal and meaningful relationships with stakeholders.

- Designate a dedicated internal ambassador responsible for communication
- Share tangible project outcomes with stakeholders to demonstrate progress or invite stakeholders to the sites
- Go beyond transactional engagements, fostering trust and collaboration

Suggested activity: E-mail newsletters, regular updates meeting, field visit

Create more targeted messages.

- Incorporate discussions on tangible economic impacts, job creation, and market relevance to highlight the project's real-world significance
- Tailor engagement strategies to be context-specific, acknowledging the diversity within farming communities and territories
- Utilize ChatGPT to facilitate seamless and responsive communication with stakeholders

Get away from stereotypes.

- Present P2Green and your pilot in a professional and progressive image – steering away from the "hippie, poeplie" image

Suggested activity: Blog entries, E-mail newsletters

Draw insights from climate debate.

- Learn valuable lessons from debates surrounding climate issues. Adapt successful engagement strategies from these discussions. E.g. join the broader discussion, collaborate with new actors e.g. social media <https://www.dlr.org/de/landwirtschaft/pressenotizen/1/news/19-acthor-international-geo-influencer-tweets>

Create emotions!

- Adopt innovative and non-normative approaches to engage stakeholders. Explore the use of entertainment, storytelling, and emotionally resonant content to capture attention. Create connections, and foster a deeper understanding of our initiatives

Suggested actions: Blog entries, Social Media posts and collaborations, Blog entry, external events

4 Activities.

Regular Meetings with relevant stakeholders/ Updates/ Town Hall meetings
To create a "Beginners' list" of stakeholders for your pilot region. To keep stakeholders engaged who are interested in the progress of the project. Present outcomes from your pilot region. Engage experts in the debate.

Target: Policy makers, experts, NGOs, Farmers representatives
Frequency: Every 6 months

External events
Sign and participate in events in your region to promote P2GreenN. Participate in the events of your stakeholders. Participate in the local network's events.

Target: Experts, Academics, Partner projects, NGOs, Policy makers, Farmers' representatives, Local authorities, etc.
Frequency: On demand

Info days, events, workshops and open discussion, field visits
Organize info days, field visits or workshops to show your test site to your stakeholders.

Target: Experts, Academics, Partner projects, NGOs, Policy makers, Farmers' representatives, Local authorities, etc.
Frequency: every 12 months

Share dissemination and information material
Share dissemination material of the project and your test site in local newspapers, local venues, press releases, etc.

Target: General public, Experts, Academics, Partner projects, NGOs, Policy makers, Farmers representatives, etc.
Frequency: every 6 months

Door-to-door and 1:1 communication
Hold informal communication to spread the word and create awareness. Have physical and online dissemination material by hand to spread the word.

Target: General public, Experts, Academics, Partner projects, NGOs, Policy makers, Farmers representatives, etc.
Frequency: Continuously

5 Social Media Outreach/ Blog Entry

Updates on the project to reach out to the public. Rep-ogt of project's social media content. Create and share blog entries. Collaborate with other projects, NGOs, or influencers to share and link content.

Target: General public, Experts, Academics, Partner projects, NGOs, Policy makers, Farmers representatives, etc.
Frequency: on demand – SoMe (twice a month) – Blog entry (every three months)

Emails/ Newsletters on pilot level/ Press release
To create continuous communication with your stakeholders. Present outcomes on the pilot level, your technologies, your plans, your connection to the region etc.

Target: General public, Experts, Academics, Partner projects, NGOs, Policy makers, Farmers representatives, etc.
Frequency: every 3 months

Appendix D.1: Stakeholder engagement calendar Germany

Suggested Events	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030	2031	2032	2033	2034	2035	2036	2037	2038	2039	2040	2041	2042	2043	2044	2045	2046	
Regular Meetings with relevant stakeholders/ Updates/ Town Hall meetings																									
External events																									
Info days, events, workshops and open discussion, field visits																									
Information campaign																									
Share dissemination material (e.g. in person, article etc.)																									
Social Media Outreach/ Blog entries																									
Door-to-door communication, 1:1 communication																									
Email/ Newsletters on pilot level/ Press release																									
Survey/ questionnaires																									

Appendix D.2: Stakeholder engagement plan Spain

Spain.
Community Engagement Plan.

2 Stakeholder insights.

From your first stakeholder engagement workshop, we gained some insights into the challenges and needs of your local stakeholders. We also collected the potential benefits your stakeholders see in our project.

Challenges your stakeholders face:

- Challenges with network building
- Lack of mediation and administration of networks and discussions
- Lack of governance
- Overcoming societal rejection of using reclaimed water
- Lack of citizen awareness
- Accessibility to digital tools and systems on all levels (farmers/ administrators)
- Promotion of best practice
- Adapt water quality for its use

Needs of stakeholders:

- Encouragement to use different water sources
- Training in the usage of different water sources
- Awareness raising among citizens and promotion of best practices
- Implementation of sustainable agriculture and food systems
- Increased research budget
- Investment in infrastructure and sensors
- Soil recovery

Benefits for stakeholders:

- Economic savings and savings in energy, water, and fertilizer
- Nutrient/ irrigation dosing adjusted to crop needs through digitization
- Waste reduction
- Increased water availability
- Promotion of circular economy

Keep in mind about your stakeholder:

- What do they already know about the project?
- What do they need to know?
- Their power to affect or influence the project.
- Their interest and sentiment toward the project.

3 Engagement strategies.

General:

Create targeted and effective messages!

- ✓ Decide who you want to communicate to
- ✓ Decide what you want to communicate
- ✓ Decide on the most effective channel to communicate
- ✓ Decide on the right timeframe to communicate

Build synergies with similar projects and their stakeholders.

- ✓ Scan the outreach activities of other projects, participate in their events, and co-create events. Use the stakeholder calendar to keep the overview

Be proactive!

- ✓ Research on activities of stakeholders and join these events
- ✓ Be present in online- and offline appearances and events of your stakeholders
- ✓ Invite stakeholders to 5min conversations to engage them

Use the language of your stakeholders.

- ✓ Translate all out-reach activities to Spanish
- ✓ Adjust your message and tone to your audience

Create incentives for stakeholders to join your events or get curious about your activities!

- ✓ Provide stakeholders with fruits as samples
- ✓ Create a story around your test-site and show what stakeholders can gain from your activities

Increase communication and visibility!

- ✓ Understand which media you want to use e.g., online newsletter, flyers in local authorities or venues, local newspaper, participation at local events etc.
- ✓ Creating local social media channels (think about the time and effort connected to it and make sure you can maintain the account)

Think outside of your existing context.

- ✓ Consider stakeholders from other sectors (e.g., gardening, landscape, etc.) to apply your solutions
- ✓ Think broad and scale up also to address stakeholders who are not directly connected to the project

4 Activities.

Regular meetings with relevant stakeholders/ Updates/ Town Hall meetings
To create a community of Stakeholders for your pilot region. To engage interested stakeholders and create an expert discussion around your activities. Present outcomes from your pilot region. Engage experts in the debate.

Target: Policy makers, experts, NGOs, Farmers representatives

Frequency: Every 6 months

External events
Scan and participate in events in your region to promote P2GreenN. Participate in the events of your stakeholders. Participate in the local network's events.

Target: Experts, Academics, Partner projects, NGOs, Policy makers, Farmers representatives etc.

Frequency: On demand

Info days, events, training workshops and open discussion, field visits
Organize info days, field visits or workshops to show your test site to your stakeholders.

Target: Experts, Academics, Partner projects, NGOs, Policy makers, Farmers representatives etc.

Frequency: every 12 months

Share dissemination and information material
Share dissemination material of the project and your test site in local newspapers, local venues, press releases etc.

Target: General public, Experts, Academics, Partner projects, NGOs, Policy makers, Farmers representatives etc.

Frequency: every 6 months

Door-to-door and 1:1 communication
Hold informal communication *as a way to* spread the word and create awareness. Have physical and online dissemination material by hand to spread the word.

Target: General public, Experts, Academics, Partner projects, NGOs, Policy makers, Farmers representatives etc.

Frequency: Continuously

Social Media Outreach/ Blog Entry
Updates on the project to reach out to the **general public**. Repost of project's social media content. Create and share blog entries. Collaborate with other projects, NGOs, or Influencers to share and link content.

Target: General public, Experts, Academics, Partner projects, NGOs, Policy makers, Farmers representatives etc.

Frequency: on demand – SoMe (twice a month) – Blog entry (every three month)

Emails/ Newsletters on pilot level/ Press release
To create continuous communication with your stakeholders. Present outcomes on the pilot level, present your technologies, your plans, your connection to the region etc.

Target: General public, Experts, Academics, Partner projects, NGOs, Policy makers, Farmers representatives etc.

Frequency: every 3 months

Appendix D.3: Stakeholder engagement calendar Spain

	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36	M37	M38	M39	M40	M41	M42	M43	M44	M45	M46
Regular Meetings with relevant stakeholders/ Updates/ Town Hall meetings						X							X							X				
External events																								
Info days, events, training workshops and open discussion, field visits									X													X		
Information campaigns																								
Share dissemination material (e.g. in person, article, etc.)																								
Social Media Outreach/ Blog entries				X					X				X					X		X				
Door to door communication, 1:1 communication																								
Email newsletters or pilot trials/ Press release	X					X				X				X								X		
Surveys/ questionnaire																								

Appendix D.4: Stakeholder engagement plan Sweden:

1 Stakeholder mapping.

As of January 2023, 60 relevant stakeholders were listed by the Swedish pilot. These include 19 local/regional, 29 national, and 12 international stakeholders. Notably, 19 stakeholders rank with low relevance, while 22 hold medium relevance, and 19 are of high relevance in the pilot region.

2 Stakeholder insights.

From your first stakeholder engagement workshop, we gained some insights into the challenges and needs of your local stakeholders. We also collected the potential benefits your stakeholders see in our project.

Challenges your stakeholders face:

- Stakeholders are busy and lack of time, interest or energy to engage
- No incentives (monetary)
- Lack of business models
- Identifying the responsible stakeholders
- Complex challenge of upscaling
- Only focus on P and no other elements
- Missing budget
- No standardized system solution
- Contact the wrong person and/or low responsiveness
- Offered stakeholder activities are perceived as "wrong" activities
- Many uncertainties (about the outcome of the project)
- The topic is not as well-known/accepted as e.g. climate
- No large scale projects or cases as best practice
- Lack of knowledge or dislike of urine diversion
- Complex topic which is hard to explain
- No offer of a centralized process

Needs of stakeholders:

- Governance and infrastructure
- Food and fertilizer security
- Augmenting the efficiency of WWTP
- Prevention of pharmaceutical, and medical residues
- Climate change mitigation
- Prevention of eutrophication (excessive growth of algae)

Benefits for stakeholders:

- Green labelled products (fertilizer, beer, etc.)
- Circular resource recovery
- Knowledge sharing on Circular Economy

3 Engagement strategies.

General:

Foster a sense of community among stakeholders.

- Amplify the project brand visibility by creating marketing material (e.g. t-shirts, pins, stickers, etc.)
- Clearly articulate the P2GreenN vision, mission, and goals to align stakeholders around a common purpose

Share Best Practices.

- Disseminate best practices through workshops, webinars, or a dedicated online portal, to share lessons learned and innovative ideas
- Plan events >3 months ahead to get the stakeholders to attend
- Implement feedback mechanisms to encourage stakeholders to share their experiences and insights (e.g. follow-up emails, feedback forms)

Suggested activity: E-mail newsletters, regular update meeting, field visit

Educational Initiatives.

- Focus on partnerships with educational stakeholders to integrate the P2GreenN project values and goals into curricular activities (e.g. P2GreenN as a case study, present fertilizer product, present process, etc.)

Suggested activity: Blog entries, E-mail newsletters, external events (lectures)

Draw Insights from Climate Debate.

- Learn valuable lessons from debates surrounding climate issues. Adopt successful engagement strategies from these discussions (e.g. bring source separation to the minds of people, show the connection to people's daily activities, etc.)
- Stress the resilience of the project
- Show success stories of source separation

4 Activities.

Regular Meetings with relevant stakeholders/ Updates/ Town Hall meetings

To create a community of Stakeholders for your pilot region. To engage interested stakeholders and create an expert discussion around your activities. Present outcomes from your pilot region. Engage experts in the debate.

Target: Policy makers, experts, NGOs, farmers representatives, academics

Frequency: Every 6 months

External events

Scan and participate in events in your region to promote P2GreenN. Participate in the events of your stakeholders. Participate in the local network's events. Make use of your existing network.

Target: Experts, academics, partner projects, NGOs, policymakers, farmers representatives, etc.

Frequency: On demand

Info days, events, training workshops and open discussion, field visits

Organize info days, field visits, or workshops to show your test site to your stakeholders. Present your research, the fertilizer, and the final product.

Target: Experts, academics, partner projects, NGOs, policymakers, farmers representatives, public, etc.

Frequency: every 12 months

Share dissemination and information material

Share dissemination material of the project and your test site in local newspapers, radio, local verbius, press releases, etc. Use your network to share the material at SLU in lectures, case studies, etc.

Target: General public, experts, academics, partner projects, NGOs, policymakers, Farmers representatives, etc.

Frequency: every 6 months

Door-to-door and 1:1 communication

Hold informal communication to spread the word and create awareness. Have physical and online dissemination material by hand to spread the word through cold calls, follow-up calls emails, etc.

Viability:

Performing a survey to assess stakeholders.

- Develop a comprehensive survey to understand the preferences and expectations of our stakeholders.
- Analyze survey results to identify key areas of interest and areas for improvement

Suggested activity: Surveys/ Questionnaires

Create more targeted messages.

- Create a core message and communication material (Infographics, Info Videos)
- Align your initiatives with broader topics such as climate change to enhance relevance and impact (draw the connection of P2GreenN to the climate debate)
- Regularly issue press releases to keep stakeholders and the public informed about our initiatives, achievements, and milestones

Suggested activity: Press releases, E-mail newsletters

Be proactive!

- Focus on all dissemination channels e.g. establish targeted contacts with media outlets, including Radio P1 and P4, Land, and ATL
- Show your products and research!

Establish a connection and stay in contact with your stakeholders!

- Tailor innovative events, such as a Hackathon, to align with stakeholder interests and industry trends
- Prioritize direct communication channels such as cold calls over emails to ensure a more personal and immediate connection
- Establish a dedicated process for facilitating two-way dialogues with stakeholders within 30 minutes of their outreach
- Conduct personalized follow-up meetings to address individual stakeholder concerns and maintain strong relationships
- Plan and schedule engagements with stakeholders three months in advance to ensure effective coordination and participation

Suggested activities: Direct Emails, Calls, one-on-one meetings

Policymakers:

Keep local stakeholders informed about the impact of regulatory changes.

- Timely Communication: provide stakeholders with a policy brief outlining the effects of the new directive.

Organize Q&A sessions to address any queries or concerns arising from the new directive.

Suggested activities: Info Day, regular meetings, external events

Showcase a way out of bureaucracy.

- Illustrate the commitment to navigating and streamlining bureaucratic processes for the benefit of the pilot stakeholders

Technical Innovation (Urinats/Urine Division):

- Embrace and communicate advancements in urinal technology and urine diversion practices, highlighting our commitment to technical innovation and green transition

Show up at events of stakeholders:

- Emphasize the importance of personal presence - both physically and virtually - in all engagement activities.
- Encourage pilot team members to actively participate in industry events, conferences, and stakeholder meetings to build strong, face-to-face connections

Explore Funds opportunities

- Establish a dedicated team or individual responsible for identifying and securing funds to support engagement initiatives
- Explore partnerships, sponsorships, and grant opportunities to ensure sustainable funding for impactful engagement programs

Suggested activity: regular update meetings with representatives of policymakers, field visits

Project Number:
Project Acronym:

101081883
P2Green
Deliverable 4.3

Target: General public, experts, academics, partner projects, NGOs, policymakers, farmers representatives, etc.
Frequency: Continuously

Social Media Outreach/ Blog Entry
Updates on the project to reach out to the public. Report of project's social media content. Create and share blog entries. Collaborate with other projects, NGOs, or influencers to share and link content. Make use of your existing network to share your story!

Target: General public, experts, academics, partner projects, NGOs, policymakers, farmers representatives, etc.
Frequency: on demand – SoMe (twice a month) – Blog entry (every three months)

Emails/ Newsletters on pilot level/ Press release
To create continuous communication with your stakeholders. Present outcomes on the pilot level, present your technologies, your plans, your connection to the region, etc.
Target: General public, experts, academics, partner projects, NGOs, policymakers, Farmers representatives, etc.
Frequency: every 3 month

Appendix D.5: Stakeholder engagement calendar Sweden

	X	Y	Z	AA	AB	AC	AD	AE	AF	AG	AH	AI	AJ	AK	AL	AM	AN	AO	AP	AQ	AR	AS	AT	AU
Suggested Events	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36	M37	M38	M39	M40	M41	M42	M43	M44	M45	M46
Events																								
Regular Meetings with relevant stakeholders/ Stakeholder Town Hall meetings					X						X									X				
External events																								
Info days, events, training workshops and open discussion, field visits									X													X		
Information campaigns																								
Share dissemination material (e.g. in person, article etc.)																								
Social Media Outreach/ Blog entries				X					X			X					X				X			
Door to door communication, 1:1 communication																								
Emails/ Newsletters on pilot level/ Press release		X				X				X			X					X					X	
Surveys/ questionnaire																								

Appendix E: Feedback survey

Q12.1. The tool was helpful to identify and map stakeholders.

■ Strongly Disagree ■ Disagree ■ Neither Agree Nor Disagree ■ Somewhat Agree ■ Strongly Agree

Q12.2. We used the list of stakeholders (stakeholder database) in further activities.

■ Strongly Disagree ■ Disagree ■ Neither Agree Nor Disagree ■ Somewhat Agree ■ Strongly Agree

Q13.1. It was easy to use this tool and it helped us to identify challenges and needs of our stakeholders.

■ Strongly Disagree ■ Disagree ■ Neither Agree Nor Disagree ■ Somewhat Agree ■ Strongly Agree

Q13.2. We used the listed challenges and needs in further activities.

■ Strongly Disagree ■ Disagree ■ Neither Agree Nor Disagree ■ Somewhat Agree ■ Strongly Agree

Contact

Programme Coordinator:

agrathaer GmbH

Eberswalder Straße 84, 15374 Müncheberg

Tel.: +49 33432 82 149

Info@agrathaer.de

www.p2green.eu

www.facebook.com/p2greenHorizonEU

<https://www.linkedin.com/in/p2green-horizon-eu-72aba1259/>

www.instagram.com/p2green/

www.twitter.com/P2green_Horizon

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, under Grant Agreement No°**101081883**.